

21NRM06 EMC-STD

D2: Report on the traceable radiated electromagnetic emissions measurement methods optimised for in situ assessment of large-size/high power equipment, including: i) validated test procedures along with the characterisation of influence factors and a measurement protocol for selecting adequate test setup (i.e., antenna location, height, and polarisation) and ii) data from CISPR 37-based test site investigations, radiated emissions test results, including comparison data, and iii) time domain technique for fast electrical and magnetic radiated emission testing to capture worst case emissions and short duration/transient interference.

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
AF	Antenna Factor
AV	Average (detector)
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
CF	Conversion Factor
CISPR	Comité International Spécial des Perturbations Radioélectriques
CW	Continuous Wave
DAC	Digital-to-Analog Converter
DC	Direct Current
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
dref	Reference Distance
dm	Measurement Distance
EUT	Equipment Under Test
EM	Electromagnetic
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
EV	Electric Vehicle
FD	Frequency Domain
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LISN	Line Impedance Stabilizing Network
MC	Mutual Coupling
MSLA	Multi-axis Shielded Loop Antenna
NSA	Normalized Site Attenuation
OATS	Open Area Test Site
OL	Overlap Factor
PDF	Probability Distribution Function
PELT	Pruned Exact Linear Time
PK	Peak (detector)

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D2 REPORT

PRF	Pulse Repetition Frequency
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
PV	Photovoltaic
QP	Quasi-Peak (detector)
RBW	Resolution Bandwidth
SIL	Site Insertion Loss
SLA	Shielded Loop Antenna
SMPS	Switched Mode Power Supply
STFT	Short-Time Fourier Transform
TD	Time Domain

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Executive summary

This report, prepared under the EMC-STD project (21NRM06), addresses the development of traceable radiated electromagnetic emissions measurement methods optimized for in situ assessment of large-size and high-power equipment. Current standards, such as CISPR 11, provide limited guidance for testing outside standardized sites, leaving significant gaps for atypical installations like photovoltaic systems, cranes, and electric vehicle charging infrastructure. To bridge these gaps, the forthcoming CISPR 37 standard proposes methodologies for in situ measurements, including alternative distances and correction factors. This deliverable consolidates validated test procedures, influence factor characterization, and protocols for selecting appropriate setups, alongside data from CISPR 37-based investigations and advanced time-domain techniques.

The report introduces comprehensive methodologies for electric and magnetic field measurements in real-world environments, emphasizing planning, ambient noise characterization, and adaptive measurement strategies. Practical campaigns conducted on photovoltaic installations demonstrate the feasibility of these approaches, highlighting challenges such as environmental noise and site constraints. Results confirm that emissions primarily originate from inverter units, with electric field levels occasionally exceeding limits, while magnetic field emissions generally remain compliant. These findings underscore the importance of flexible measurement axes, distance correction, and robust analysis to ensure accurate compliance assessments.

A major innovation presented is the integration of time-domain measurement systems, which drastically reduce testing time from hours to seconds while improving accuracy. Techniques such as multi-resolution bandwidth analysis, time gating, and amplitude probability distribution enable differentiation between equipment emissions and ambient noise, even in harsh electromagnetic environments. Additionally, the report explores rapid emissions checks for installers using affordable instruments, aiming to detect major EMC issues early without replacing formal compliance tests.

Further contributions include the derivation and experimental validation of distance conversion factors for magnetic field limits between 9 kHz and 30 MHz. These factors, expressed through piecewise linear models, allow practical application when measurements cannot be performed at the reference 10 m distance. Investigations into site insertion loss (SIL) across multiple environments—open area, mosque courtyard, and car park—reveal deviations influenced by reflections and obstacles, reinforcing the need for pre-validation of test sites.

The document also introduces a Multi-axis Shielded Loop Antenna (MSLA) combined with multichannel digitizers, enabling simultaneous three-axis measurements and phase tracking. This approach mitigates mutual coupling effects through correction algorithms, achieving high precision comparable to conventional single-axis methods while significantly reducing measurement time. Such advancements support realistic testing scenarios, including transient detection and dynamic operating modes, without compromising accuracy.

In conclusion, Deliverable 2 fulfills its objectives by providing a robust framework for in situ radiated emissions testing. The proposed methodologies enhance efficiency, reliability, and adaptability, contributing to the evolution of EMC standards and ensuring better protection of the radio spectrum. These innovations are expected to influence future guidelines for large-scale industrial and renewable energy installations, aligning compliance practices with emerging technological and environmental challenges.

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1. Introduction

Although CISPR 11 emphasizes the need for measurements of large and high-power equipment in industrial environments only for radiated emissions, the performance and characterisation and also the correlation of the method with the real radiated emission measurement are very open in CISPR 11 and need exhaustive research [1]. One standard under development (the CISPR 37 Ed. 1.0) is intended to bridge the gaps left by CISPR 11 in terms of in situ testing, outside standardised test sites. This document describes the test procedures and measurement configurations for in-situ radiated (electric and magnetic) emissions developed during this research project [2].

Examples of large and high-power equipment that cannot be tested on standard test sites are (photovoltaic) PV systems, cranes, automatic storage systems, some elements of the (electric vehicle) EV charging infrastructure on the road. These target use cases have been emphasized during the CISPR37 meetings. Dr. Yasutoshi Yoshioka, one of the leading members of the CISPR and IEC on the topic of EMC for photovoltaics and Manager at the European Research & Technical Center of Fuji Electric, is a key promoter of the CISPR 37 project to fill this gap. Dr. Yoshioka, the project's Chief Stakeholder, seeks to answer the need for a standard about EMC assessments of large and high-power equipment performed in situ or at defined sites. Its ultimate goal is, therefore, contributing to the protection of the radio spectrum and complying with the EMC Directive requirements.

For radiated emission testing, the draft standard CISPR 37 aims for tests of atypical equipment that cannot be tested on a standard test site due to the physically large size and high power. It also proposes test methods at the distances other than the reference distance (10 m) with the use of some proposed correction factors and windowing techniques. In this concept, CISPR 37-based test site investigations were performed with NSA/SIL techniques including distance conversion factors, effects of nearby installations/buildings, etc. Most measurements in this workpackage were done jointly by consortium members or stakeholders. For that reason, some restrictions may apply in terms of photo of EUTs and test environments, but data were provided and published in literature.

The new methods proposed by draft standards were implemented and thoroughly studied and verified in actual test environments. The project studied on the electrical and magnetic field radiated emission test methods, test site validation techniques and correction factors proposed by the draft CISPR 37 standard in the frequency range of 150 kHz – 1 GHz. The project also studied measuring the worst radiated emission case of the EUT such as impulsive-transient or short duration emissions by applying full time domain EMI measurements to support CISPR 37 and other standards dealing with atypical device tests. The assessment of the operating modes and worst-case emissions, including transient emission, of different EUT were investigated using time domain techniques in front of conventional frequency domain analysis. A drastic reduction of measurement time, from hours to less than a minute, were achieved using time-domain methods.

2. Methodology

This section describes the measurement setups, procedures followed and relevant data for radiated measurements, comparison of test sites based on CISPR 37, time-domain measurement procedures and comparison of time-domain vs frequency-domain measurements.

2.1 In-situ radiated measurement methods and procedures

Under this title, it is presented the methodology and the results of a joint measurement campaign carried out at photovoltaic installation. The main objective is to demonstrate in situ emissions measurement procedures in the use case of photovoltaic systems. Since the measurement location is private property of Fuji Electric, photographs from measurements are not available.

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In this action, a team of EMC Experts, including members on their respective National EMC standardizations committees, collaborated to improve current procedures and to find consensus with regards to the best engineering and testing practices to address the complicated problem of the electromagnetic emissions assessment in situ.

The methodology applied is described including details about the instrumentation, the test site characteristics and the rationale for the selection of the more suited measurement points.

The study comprises two different PV installations, System A and System B. Both are part of same big installation, but, found in two different buildings.

A time domain measuring receiver (CISPR 16-1-1 complaint) is used as a primary tool. Magnetic field emissions are measured from 150 kHz to 30 MHz using a 60 cm loop antenna. Electric field emissions are measured in the frequency range from 30 MHz to 1 GHz using a Bilog Hybrid antenna. The QP measure is obtained directly.

The procedures applied are adequate for their intended purpose as they allow for:

- Complementary/Preliminary measurements.
- Identification of frequencies of highest emissions.
- Definition of representative measurement points and axes.
- Characterization of ambient levels.
- Differentiation of ambient levels from EUT emissions.
- Application of distance corrected emissions limits.
- Evaluation of the results.

Measures from PV System A are detected both in H-field and E-field. The point with higher emissions is in front of the three inverters. In the case of E-field, it is found that emissions from the EUT are above the limit.

Measures from PV system B show no significant emissions produced by the EUT. Nonetheless, it is detected external noise sources, such as a machinery room with air conditioning, motor inverters, etc. with a high emission level.

2.1.1 General Setup

2.1.1.1 Equipment

Table 1. Equipment for measurement

Brand	Model	Description
Schwarzbeck	VULB9168	Electric field antenna
ETS LINDGREN	6512	Loop antenna
Intertek	ZFL-500	Preamplifier 50 kHz to 1 GHz (~25 dB).
Intertek	ZHL-6A	Preamplifier 2.5 kHz to 500 MHz (~25 dB).
Agilent	8491B	6 dB attenuator
HUBER+SUHNER	6803.17.B	6 dB attenuator
Rohde&Schwarz	RTO64	Oscilloscope S/N: 101322

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EMC BCN	emiGO	TD measuring software. Associated with calibration certificate 1013-KL-60031-23.
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2.1.1.2 Measurement setup

The following measurement elements were used.

- For E-field measures, from 30 MHz to 1 GHz, VULB9168 antenna was used connected to ZFL-500 preamplifier. No input attenuator was used except at some measurement points, as stated in this report. Height = 2 m.

emiGO was configured in such frequency range with an acquisition time of 10 ms, a sampling rate of 5 GSa/s, and a resolution of 10 bit.

- For H-field measures, from 150 kHz to 30 MHz, ETS LINDGREN 6512 passive loop antenna was used connected to ZFL-6A preamplifier. No input attenuator was used. Height = 1.3 m (floor to center).

emiGO was configured in such frequency range with an acquisition time of 100 ms, a sampling rate of 200 MSa/s, and a resolution of 14 bit.

2.1.6.2.1 System Description

2.1.2.1 Facilities

Location facilities of the photovoltaic system is confidential.

Two different systems are assessed: the photovoltaic system can be found in two buildings, System A and System B.

2.1.2.2 System A

A consists of 3 PV inverters and several PV panels.

The rooftop has several constructions and a mobile communications base station, including its transmitting antenna.

Inverters are located on a wall. On the same wall, the junction box as well as the down transformer can be found.

Each of the 3 total inverters has a section of the PV panels. Therefore, inverter 3 (left one, regarding north orientation) is connected to 48 PV panels on the left part of the building, inverter 2 is to 48 PV panels on the center part of the building, and inverter 1 to 48 PV panels on the right of the building.

It must be remarked that cables are covered with a metallic tray connected to PE.

2.1.2.3 System B

The second evaluated system, "System B", is located on another building. In this case, the system has less PV and rated power than System A.

It is important to remark that heavy machinery (air conditioning with motors and inverters) is located above the PV panels.

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2.1.6.2.1 Measurement Conditions

Measurement conditions are summarized in the table below, depending on the time, weather conditions, and location.

Table 2. Measurement conditions

Condition	Location	Time	Meteorology
C	System A	9:41h	Sunny and clear
D	System B	14:03h	Mainly clear

Equipment, antenna, and other configurations related to test setup are described in Section 2.2.

2.1.6.2.1 General Procedures and Arrangements

For in situ electromagnetic (EM) emissions measurements, the work procedures and arrangements start before the measurement campaign and extend further after the tests are completed. In this section, the procedures followed are explained and justified in a general way. The procedure goes through several steps, as explained in what follows. However, this procedure is not linear, flowing in a single direction. Instead, it must be thought of as an adaptive methodology that may require iterations between stages, as flexibility is fundamental for in situ emissions measurement campaigns.

2.1.4.1 Planning State

Planning is fundamental for the success of the in situ emissions measurement campaign, as it gathers information, allows anticipating problems, and sets the logistics required for a smooth operation.

It is recommended that the planning stage is started well in advance of the intended in situ emissions measurement campaign, and it must be updated in case of contingency.

The planning stage includes:

- A revision of the EUT documentation to identify potential sources and frequencies of electromagnetic emissions. This documentation includes the manual, schematics, instructions, etc.
- A visual inspection of the EUT and the surroundings of the test site. The floor plan and electrical schematic should be checked. The accessibility of the place should be considered.
- To allocate the resources needed to install and operate the measurement setup. This includes the mains power connection, power cord extenders, tables, chairs, trolleys, etc.
- The definition of the Test Plan, including the EUT boundary, the proposed measurement axes and points, and a list of operating modes.

In the case of in situ emissions measurements carried out outdoors, the weather forecast should be checked regularly, and the planning must be adjusted if necessary. Measurements should not be conducted under adverse meteorological conditions, including rain, snow, or high winds.

When: Weeks or days before the measurement campaign.

2.1.4.2 Environment Characterization Stage

Measuring the ambient noise in terms of the field strength levels in the frequency range intended for the emissions assessment is necessary. For this purpose, having the EUT turned off while the said characterization is performed is convenient.

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Then, we identify signals and noise sources from the surroundings at the measured ambient levels. It might be necessary to mitigate the impact of emissions sources different from the EUT in the same environment, turning them off or moving them away whenever possible.

Finally, we note the frequency ranges in which the ambient levels exceed the emissions limits adjusted at the measurement distance.

The ambient noise levels are monitored in real-time to identify transient events and sudden changes in electromagnetic noise that may compromise the test results. In case of unstable ambient levels, emissions measurements must be halted. If ambient level measurements are presumed to be affected by transient noise, such measurement must be repeated.

In test sites with a radio transmitter near the measuring antenna, e.g., mobile base stations located on rooftops, extra precautions should be taken to prevent distorted results due to saturation effects at the measuring receiver or in the preamplifier. Filtering or extra attenuation of the received signal might be required.

When: Just before the start of the measurement campaign. In parallel to 2.1.4.2

2.1.4.3 Selection of the Measurement Axes and Points

The selection of the measurement axes and points is an informed decision. It can be based on:

- a) Documentary evidence and expert judgment,
- b) Test site restrictions and time constraints
- c) Complementary measurements
- d) A combination of the previous.

In all cases, the rationale for the selection of the measurement axes and points must be detailed in the test report as it is a multifactorial decision and it is made on a case-by-case basis.

In this context, complementary measurements provide extra information that the EMC Expert uses to make decisions regarding the appropriate setup and deployment of the in situ emissions measurement campaigns.

Complementary measurements are not intended for compliance checking. Conversely, they contribute to reducing the risks of mistakes and false assumptions in the testing process.

Examples of complementary measurements are:

- Surveying the electromagnetic emissions around the EUT. This includes, for example, near-field scanning using portable instruments and handy antennas.
- Measuring the EUT emissions at distances that are shorter than the reference distance but using the same setup as per the definitive measurements.
- RF current measurements using clamping probes.

The exact procedure followed for the complementary measurements and all elements used for their sake must be explained in the test report.

The exact number of measurement axes should be confirmed. Following the test plan criterion, at least 4 different measurement axes are considered around the EUT boundary. However, it is recommended that at least one measurement axis is defined per the identified EUT noise sources. The initially proposed measurement axis can be confirmed, modified, or expanded based on the complementary measurements.

Those measurement axes should be distributed around the different sides of the EUT boundary. The measurement axes should be perpendicular to the side of the EUT boundary. The measurement distances are determined over the measurement axes.

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When possible, we perform measurements at different distances for each measurement axis. In particular, the recommended measurement distances are 3 m, 5 m, and 10 m. The distances over the measurement axes are measured from the EUT boundary to the outside. The measurement points are marked on the floor. No measurement point is defined inside the boundary.

It is advised to define a sequence to run the different measurements (axes and points), prioritizing those that are more likely to exhibit higher emission levels.

When: Just before the start of the measurement campaign. In parallel to 2.1.4.2.

2.1.4.4 Emissions Assessment Stage

The measuring receiver, antennas, and the rest of the elements necessary for the measurements must be set-up. It is recommended that correction factors and the measurement automation software are configured beforehand.

The test procedure is iterative for all measurement points. For each measurement point:

- Measure the ambient levels for each frequency range and antenna polarization/orientation.
- Run the H-field and/or E-field strength measurements for each test condition or operating mode.

No height scan is performed.

By analyzing the measurement results at different distances and over the same axes, we can decide if the field level versus distance trend is coherent. Also, we can confirm if the field levels measured are due to the EUT or not.

For each measurement axes, one of its measurement points is decided to be labeled as a final measurement. This measurement point is upon which a decision will be made. The selection of the measurement point for the final results is made prioritizing the conclusiveness of the results according to this rule:

- a) In sufficiently good conditions of ambient noise levels, measurement points at a distance equal to the reference distance are preferred.
- b) If a measurement point at the reference distance is not feasible, then it is preferred to approach the antenna to the EUT boundary, up to 3 m and apply the corresponding distance conversion factors to the emissions limits.
- c) Axes with less than 3 m distance between the EUT boundary and the measuring antenna should not be considered.

In case the results obtained don't lead to a clear conclusion, further analysis is required. This may include new measurement points, deeper analysis that allow correlating the measured spectrum with the EUT behavior, spectrum recalculation/measurement with narrower RBW, etc. The tailored analysis, if necessary, must be explained in the test report.

Typically, we recommend to further investigate in situ emissions test results when at the frequency of maximum emissions the results are ± 3 dB of the limits. This may include, the repetition of the critical measurement points.

If a definitive failure condition (field strengths significantly higher than the limits) has been detected at a measurement point, some of the rest of the measurement points defined in the test plan can be omitted.

When: Just after 2.1.4.3 is done.

2.1.4.5 Analysis and Reporting Stage

The results are to be fully processed after the measurement campaign. This is because some details can't be checked in detail while in situ due to practical and time limitations.

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It is recommendable to hold a meeting to review the results.

For the report, the results are organized, summarized, presented and analysed in order to reach a high confidence decision on whether the in situ tested EUT or fixed installations.

Also, the report must contain the information about all the relevant complementary measurements or information involved in the decision made throughout all the process. The report should be clear and explicit, so it is possible to understand the situation, the observations and the conclusions.

The photographic record is indispensable to keep track of the test conditions.

It is recommendable to have the data available alongside the report file.

When: In the days that follow the measurement campaign.

2.1.6.2.1 Rationale for Measurements Points

Based on the planning stage, for both scenarios considered, the main source of the emissions was identified as the inverters. The inverters are where all the switching takes place, therefore, it is the origin of the EUT's high frequency noise.

For the rest, the measurement axes were distributed to cover the different sides of the EUT boundary. Along each proposed measurement axes, measurement points were defined at either 3 m, 5 m and/or 10 m, following the general explanation given in 5.3.

In the System A; PV installation, the inverters were mounted on the wall while some direct current (DC) and alternate current (AC) cables exited the inverter enclosure running in vertical until they reached the floor. Some of those cables run inside the metallic tray. Some others may connect to the electrical panel around the corner.

Based on this analysis, the measurement axis A is defined perpendicular to the central face of the inverters of System A. Along this axis, measurement points at 3 m, 5 m and 10 m are selected because the site allows it.

Because of the disposition, the measurement axis A is defined as the top priority.

Measurement axis C is defined perpendicular to Axis A, also covering the potential influence of radiation coming from the cabling going to the electrical panel. The measurement distance is set from the EUT boundary set at the edge of the metallic tray. The measurement distances were 3 m and 5 m. The distance between the antenna and the central point of the inverters was approximately 8 m.

Measurement axes C and D are intended to measure the emissions of the PV panels installation under the hypothesis that the long wiring scheme may act as an efficient low frequency antenna. The cables running on the edge of the EUT boundary run through a solid metallic tray which is grounded. The metallic tray effect is assumed to provide some shielding effect.

The expectation is that measurement points along axes C and D will exhibit lower emissions than those over the axes A and B.

For the System B PV installation, the measurement axes were set in such a manner that they point to the inverters from the outside of the EUT boundary.

Axes F and H are centered symmetrically in between the two rows of PV panels. In this case we have the maximum distance with respect to the inverter, so assuming they are again the main source of electromagnetic noise, then the emissions expected from their direct radiation will be attenuated on the receiver antenna end.

Axes G and I are those close to the inverters. In the case of axis G, it only allows for 3 m distance H-field measurements. The metallic structure of the panels may introduce some shielding in that direction. Finally, Axis I is where there are higher chances of obtaining significant results. Measurement points at 3 m, 5 m and

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10m are defined along axis I. As the measurement points get more distance from the EUT boundary, they approach other electrical and electronic systems placed in the rooftop.

Therefore, for the System A PV installation, the prioritized point is at 3 m of measurement distance along axis I.

2.1.5.1 System A

A total of 4 different axes are assessed

The description is the following:

- For Point A, three different distances are assessed for H-field and E-field: 3 m, 5 m, and 10 m. Point A focuses on the direct axis of the inverters.
- For Point C, H-field and E-field are assessed at 3 m and 5 m. Point C distance is measured from the boundary, in such case, from the metallic tray close to the inverters.
- For Point D, H-field and E-field are assessed at 3 m and 5 m. The distance to the antenna phase center is measured from the boundary edge, in such cases, from the metallic tray. In that position, the E-field level was so strong due to the mobile base station, so extra attenuation (12 dB) should be added to the input of the preamplifier to avoid saturation distortion.
- For Point D, only H-field is assessed at 3 m, 5 m, and 10 m. E-field is not considered due to the high E-field levels.

2.1.5.2 System B

A total of 4 different axes are assessed.

The description is the following:

- For Point F, E-field and H-field are assessed at 3 m and 5 m.

Unfortunately, due to an incident with VULB antenna, the E-field could not be measured from this point forward.

- For Point G, H-field is assessed at 3 m.
- For Point H, H-field is assessed at 3 m, 5 m and 10 m.
- For Point I, H-field is assessed at 3 m, 5 m.

2.1.6.2.1 Measurements Summary

In this section, measurement data for all points is presented. Data is summarized for each point, and limits are plotted as well.

For E-field, CISPR 37 CD2 E-field limit at 10 m is presented. A limit at 3 m is computed assuming far-field conditions.

For the H-field, the CISPR 37 CD2 H-field limit at 10 m is presented. A limit at 3 m is computed employing conversion factors proposed in such a standard.

Additional measures at 5 m or other distances are performed to identify and ensure that the PV system produces the detected emissions.

2.1.6.1 Nomenclature

Each measure is identified uniquely by its name. The name of each measure is specified as the following example:

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- **250204** → Date (YYYY - MM - DD). In this example, February 4 of 2025.
- **E** → E for E-field and H for H-field.
- **03** → Measuring distance in meters: 03, 05 or 10.
- **B** → Antenna: B for trilob antenna and H for loop antenna.
- **H** → Polarity: H (Horizontal) / V (vertical) for E-field & X / Y / Z for H-field.
- **C** → Condition: C or D in this measurement campaign.
- **PA** → Measuring point/axis. In this case, "Point A".
- **00** → Unique measure identifier. If a measure in the same conditions, point, and location is repeated, this field increments.

Note: when several measures (3 m, 5 m, and 10 m) are combined in a single plot, the distance in the title is arbitrarily 3 m. For figure captions on next subsection, date, distance, and unique identifier are ignored.

2.1.6.2 System A Results

2.1.6.2.1 Point A.

First of all, the H-field at Point A is measured at 3 m, 5 m and 10 m. Results are shown in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 4 respectively.

Figure 1. Measure HX_C_PA.

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At x-axis, it can be observed how emissions at 200 kHz – 400 kHz decrease as distance increases. Based on this observation, it is highly likely that those emissions are from the EUT. Emissions remain below the limit for all distances.

Figure 2. Measure HY_C_PA.

For y-axis, it can be observed the same behaviour at 300 kHz – 1 MHz and 2.2 MHz – 3 MHz, and 4.5 MHz – 6 MHz.

The spectrum of the wide band emissions centered at 2.8 MHz as shown in Figure 2 for a 3 m measurement distance has been re-computed employing a RBW (Resolution Bandwidth) of 500 Hz. It is observed that the frequency distance between harmonics is about 10 kHz (Figure 3), which is the operating frequency of the inverter. This finding assures that such wide-band emissions is produced by the EUT. Individual harmonics are not visible when employing standard CISPR16 RBW.

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Figure 3. Spectrum of HY_C_PA with RBW = 500 Hz.

Figure 4. Measure HZ_C_PA.

From the H-field emissions measured on the z-axis the levels remain below the limit and no further conclusions are extracted. For E-field measures, results of vertical and horizontal polarization are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6 respectively.

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05-02-2025 10:19:42

250205_E03_BV_C_PA_00

Antena: B | Polarization: V | Condition: C | Point: PA | Identifier: 00

Figure 5. Measure BV_C_PA.

A band exceeding the limit can be observed between 50 MHz and 60 MHz. Such band decreases as distance of the antenna-EUT increases.

05-02-2025 10:18:36

250205_E03_BH_C_PA_00

Antena: B | Polarization: H | Condition: C | Point: PA | Identifier: 00

Figure 6. Measure BH_C_PA.

On horizontal polarization, the dominant emissions frequencies are centred at 200 MHz. The emissions behavior with the distance remains coherent, confirming the source is the EUT.

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2.1.6.2.2 Point C.

Summary of measure taken at Point C for H-field at x-axis, y-axis and z-axis is plotted on Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 respectively.

Figure 7. Measure HX_C_PC.

Figure 8. Measure HY_C_PC.

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05-02-2025 11:01:54

Figure 9. Measure HZ_C_PC.

No exceeding of the limits can be observed in such axes.

For E-field, results of vertical and horizontal polarization are shown on Figure 10 and Figure 11 respectively.

05-02-2025 11:19:20

Figure 10. Measure BV_C_PC.

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For vertical polarization, spectrum of 3 m and 5 m measures is practically identical. From approximately 35 MHz to 70 MHz ambient levels are too close to the limit making difficult to have a definitive conclusion about the emissions in that frequency range.

05-02-2025 11:21:01

250205_E03_BH_C_PC_00

Antena: B | Polarization: H | Condition: C | Point: PC | Identifier: 00

Figure 11. Measure BH_C_PC.

For horizontal polarization, some narrowbands centered at 100 MHz can be observed at 3 m with an amplitude slightly higher than 40 dBuV/m. This is consistent with the behaviour observed in axis A. Such emissions are below limit.

2.1.6.2.3 Point D.

Results of point D are shown below.

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Figure 12. Measure HX_C_PD.

For x-axis, some emissions seem to exceed the limit above 20 MHz. However, the level at 5 m is higher than 3 m, so, it is discarded that such emissions provide from the EUT.

Figure 13. Measure HY_C_PD.

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05-02-2025 11:46:28

250205_H03_HZ_C_PD_00

Antena: H | Polarization: Z | Condition: C | Point: PD | Identifier: 00

Figure 14. Measure HZ_C_PD.

Although E-field is measured, this position required to employ higher attenuation input (due to the presence of a mobile communications antenna), therefore, increasing the noise floor above the limit in ranges above 700 MHz.

05-02-2025 11:31:56

250205_E03_BV_C_PD_00

Antena: B | Polarization: V | Condition: C | Point: PD | Identifier: 00

Figure 15. Measure BV_C_PD.

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For vertical polarization, it seems a band is barely above the limit at 70 MHz. Considering the ambient levels are very close to the emissions limits, it is recommendable to base the final decision not only on this result. Considering that measurement along axis A already detected a clear exceedance of the emissions, this result can be considered as complementary or reinforcing the previous findings.

Figure 16. Measure BH_C_PD.

2.1.6.2.4 Point E.

For Point E, only H-field is measure due to the very close presence of a mobile communications antenna that caused strong saturation above for the band above 30 MHz. Nonetheless, no valid conclusion can be extracted from such results, since emissions at 5 m are higher or equal than the emissions at 3 m or 10 m, therefore, probably are due to other source in the environment.

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05-02-2025 12:18:32

250205_H03_HX_C_PE_00

Antena: H | Polarization: X | Condition: C | Point: PE | Identifier: 00

Figure 17. Measure HX_C_PE.

05-02-2025 12:19:13

250205_H03_HY_C_PE_00

Antena: H | Polarization: Y | Condition: C | Point: PE | Identifier: 00

Figure 18. Measure HY_C_PE.

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05-02-2025 12:09:29

Figure 19. Measure HZ_C_PE.

2.1.6.2.5 Conclusions

From all the points, it is confirmed that the maximum emissions are observed along axis A, this is, focusing directly on the inverter of the PV system. Although, emissions are identified on H-field and E-field, only emissions for E-field exceeds the limit.

In this case, no strong emissions from the PV panels are detected.

2.1.6.3 System B Results

Important remark: Other noise sources different from the PV system are present. This effect is observed in the results and lead to apparent inconsistencies that must be carefully interpreted. Such noise sources in the environment can not be mitigated or turned off. This effect is found on Point F and Point I mainly.

By inspection is corroborated that heavy machinery is installed on the building near the PV panels as well as on the rooftop.

No explanation of every point is therefore conducted in this section. Final conclusions of measurements can be found on Section 2.1.6.3.5

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2.1.6.3.1 Point F.

Figure 20. Measure HX_D_PF.

Figure 21. Measure HY_D_PF.

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Figure 22. Measure HZ_D_PF.

05-02-2025 14:52:46

Figure 23. Measure BV_D_PF.

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2.1.6.3.2 Point G.

05-02-2025 15:11:38

Figure 24. Measure HX_D_PG.

05-02-2025 15:11:01

Figure 25. Measure HY_D_PG.

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05-02-2025 15:08:05

250205_H03_HZ_D_PG_00

Antena: H | Polarization: Z | Condition: D | Point: PG | Identifier: 00

Figure 26. Measure HZ_D_PG.

2.1.6.3.3 Point H.

05-02-2025 15:40:55

250205_H03_HX_D_PH_00

Antena: H | Polarization: X | Condition: D | Point: PH | Identifier: 00

Figure 27. Measure HX_D_PH.

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05-02-2025 15:41:40

250205_H03_HY_D_PH_00

Antena: H | Polarization: Y | Condition: D | Point: PH | Identifier: 00

Figure 28. Measure HY_D_PH.

05-02-2025 16:04:33

250205_H03_HZ_D_PH_00

Antena: H | Polarization: Z | Condition: D | Point: PH | Identifier: 00

Figure 29. Measure HZ_D_PH.

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2.1.6.3.4 Point I.

05-02-2025 15:53:55

Figure 30. Measure HX_D_PI.

05-02-2025 15:54:43

Figure 31. Measure HY_D_PI.

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05-02-2025 15:59:56

250205_H03_HZ_D_PI_00

Antena: H | Polarization: Z | Condition: D | Point: PI | Identifier: 00

Figure 32. Measure HZ_D_PI.

2.1.6.3.5 Conclusions.

Results show barely no significant emissions from the PV system (For example, point H, no difference between magnetic fields at different distances). However, external disturbances providing from the machinery room near the PV systems show very higher emissions that may mask the contributions from the EUT. This is why it is important to conduct measures at different distances in order to clarify and assure that electromagnetic emissions are being produced indeed by the EUT and not external elements.

2.2 CISPR 37-based test site investigations, radiated emissions test results, including comparison data

As mentioned in Section 1, work on draft standard CISPR 37 intends to find a common-base for in-situ radiated emission measurements. Research in this title presents findings of investigations on CISPR 37 based measurement methods including time-domain method.

2.2.1 Rapid Emission Checks

In-line with CISPR 37 work, CISPR SC A JWG9 project has been created to try to reach international consensus on guidelines for "Rapid Emissions Check of installations" which might guide PV systems installers on how to conduct quick checks of installations using instruments at an affordable cost compared to fully compliant EMI measuring receivers. As an outcome, it is intended to write a procedure installers can employ to determine whether their installation work has caused new EMC problems. However, this guidance is not meant to replace standard emissions tests as part of compliance assessment. Instead, it should help detect major emissions problems in the field early to fix them promptly.

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The guidance should be based on affordable and smaller instruments since installers are unlikely to invest in expensive equipment. In essence, the "Rapid Emissions Check" goal is intended to detect cases where installations emit noise significantly above the limits and give advice when more accurate measurements are required. The idea is not to compete with the more precise measurements done during conformity assessment testing.

In this context, past experiences indicate time-domain emissions measurement systems offer several advantages that make them ideal for in situ testing and rapid emissions assessments [3,4].

In what follows, it is presented a real study case where oscilloscope-based time-domain emissions measurements were used to quickly assess a PV installation located on the rooftop of a building. This empirical study allowed the identification of the main sources and emissions frequencies in situ. At the same time, our compact test setup validated the proposed approach's practical benefits.

Time-domain EMI receiver implementations have been developed for measuring and analyzing electromagnetic emissions from complex systems [5-7]. Commonly, these complex systems have behavior that changes over time and various modes of operation during normal functioning [3,4]. Because of this, the emission signature of the system under test can vary during measurement, making the frequency-swept measurement method unreliable. Moreover, when assessing emissions of atypical equipment in situ, the signals and the radiofrequency noise in the environment add further uncertainty to measurements making it even more relevant to consider the time-domain information as part of the emissions assessment [8]. Therefore, it can be concluded that time-domain EMI measurement systems are well-suited for in-situ emissions assessment.

For the measurement performed in the following sections, we used a multi-channel time-domain EMI measurement system compatible with flexible resolution deep memory oscilloscopes to capture and process EMI waveforms. Welch's method is used for spectral estimation, and adaptive windowing functions are used to set any required resolution bandwidth. For H-field emissions, the hardware used was the 4-channels USB oscilloscope PicoScope 5444B from Pico Technology. It has up to 16 bit vertical resolution, 1 GSa/s of maximum sampling rate, 200 MHz bandwidth, and memory of 512 MSa. With this configuration, CISPR 16-1-1 baseline requirements are met for CISPR bands A and B [6,9]. Conversely, a 4-channel Digital Real-time Oscilloscope Tektronix 5104B was employed for E-field measurements. It has a maximum sampling rate of 10 GSa/s and a bandwidth of 1 GHz with frequency response correction [5,10].

2.2.1.1 Measurement procedure

Radiated emissions are measured using a loop antenna (9 kHz – 30 MHz) for the magnetic field and a biconical (30 MHz – 200 MHz) and log-periodic (200 MHz - 1 GHz) for the electric field. The antennas are used with a pre-amplification stage to achieve better sensitivity. For the E-field antennas, the vertical and horizontal polarizations are assessed, and, for the H-field loop antenna, the 3 different axes (-x, -y, and -z) are considered. The height of all three antennas is 2 m. The CISPR 37 draft [11], a new standard project being developed for in-situ testing by the CIS/B Working Group 7 (WG7), has been used as a reference to apply the E-field and H-field limits. The number of points and measurement axes have been reduced in order to shorten the measurement campaign.

The Equipment Under Test (EUT) consists of a photovoltaic system inverter, shown in Figure 33. The complete system comprises 609 solar panels rated with a maximum power of 230 kWp. The entire fixed installation as well as the test site location where the measures are performed, are depicted in Figure 34.

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Figure 33 – Equipment Under Test: inverter of the photovoltaic system. The inverter is composed of two identical modules.

Figure 34 – Satellite view of the in-situ test site for the photovoltaic system studied. The PV panels are arranged over the roof. The inverter is located in the highlighted area.

In order to assess the emissions of the EUT, several measurements are performed and compared to the ambient measurement at different axes and distances (Figure 35). All combinations of polarizations, axis, and points are evaluated in order to gather as much data as possible to determine, in the most appropriate manner, the preliminary compliance of the equipment. All these measurements were carried out in a timeframe of 4 hours. During this time, more than 30 measurements were performed, including the displacement of the compact acquisition system and the relocation of the antennas. Conducting such a number of measurements using a conventional receiver would have required more than one day to finish the in-situ campaign [12]. In cases where the measuring distance differs from the reference distance (10 m), correction factors are applied as specified in the draft CISPR 37 [2].

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Figure 35 – Detailed view of the test area: reference plane, measurement axes, and measurement points. Axes are positioned at 45°, 90°, and 135° relative to the wall behind the EUT. Test points, highlighted in yellow, magenta, and blue, are situated at 3 m, 5 m, and 10 m, respectively.

2.2.1.2 Measurement results

Data was acquired, and the results were subsequently processed and analyzed off-site. Although more than 30 measurements were conducted, including the spectrum measured according to all standard weighting detectors, only the most relevant ones are shown as example. The first case examined corresponds to the magnetic field emissions. Even though the limits are only specified from 150 kHz, frequencies from 9 kHz are evaluated in order to observe the inverter's switching frequency, $f_{sw} = 16 \text{ kHz}$, and all the harmonics. The results of the 10 m point for the y-axis are displayed in Figure 36.

Figure 36 – H-field measured in the y-axis of the EUT at 10 m distance. Emissions are shown using peak measurements, PK (blue trace) as well as quasi-peak measurements, QP (green trace).

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We can notice a set of broadband emissions from 5 MHz to 30 MHz exceeding the limit. Similar bands were also detected on all the other measuring axes and at various antenna locations. Since they were not detected before the PV was installed one may conclude that the EUT is the emission source in those bands.

It is important to note that, as time-domain measurements allow for a parallel computation of all the weighting detectors, including quasi-peak (QP), it was possible to obtain the final indication directly, therefore full spectrum QP values are provided. Since the measured quasi-peak values are in the order of 20 dB above the limit EMI mitigation measures might be required to fix issues in this frequency range.

Regarding the electric field, it is more difficult to conclude the compliance of the equipment due to more variable ambient noise and a substantial discrepancy between various measurements at different points with the EUT active. Figure 37 shows the results of the electric field measured for the vertical polarization at a 10 m distance. No significant differences were found between peak and quasi-peak measurements, meaning the emissions were highly repetitive.

Figure 37 – E-field measurement in vertical polarization with the EUT active. Measurement distance is 10 m. Note the ambient is graphically overlapped by the spectrum of the emissions measured with the EUT active.

For reference purposes, ambient noise levels are displayed in Figure 38 for the corresponding antenna polarization.

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Figure 38 – Reference ambient noise measurement in vertical polarization.

As shown in Figure 37, broadband noise levels between 42 – 44 MHz and 66 – 70 MHz are close to the limit when measuring the EUT turned on. The current CISPR 37 draft proposes a preliminary measurement procedure that allows emissions measurements at closer distances to identify emissions sources. Figure 39 shows the E-field strength measured at a 5 m distance from the inverters and the amplitude of the spectrum in the said band has increased as we approached the source.

Figure 39 – Pre-scan E-field measurement in vertical polarization with the EUT active. Measurement distance is 5 m. Note the ambient is graphically overlapped by the measurement with the EUT active.

At 66 MHz the measured peak values are only slightly over a quasi-peak limit of 40 dBuV/m for a measurement distance of 10 m. Other high levels in this figure are probably regular radio services. For example FM radio broadcast from 88 to 108 MHz; DAB broadcast 174-240 MHz; Tetrapol/TETRA 380-430 MHz and 440-490 MHz, TV broadcast and mobile telephony/broadband frequency bands. However, one important observation is that the noise detected in the frequency range 30 MHz - 35 MHz should be looked at more carefully. The measurement uncertainty related to in situ measurements is high and it is hard to draw a definitive conclusions

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about whether this installation compliant with the EMC regulations. In any case, radio reception may be affected by compliant installations close to the receiving antenna. This PV inverter installation is not very likely to affect radio reception with antennas that are not near this installation. If there are receiving antennas for this frequency range in the vicinity of the installation, EMI interference mitigation might be required for this frequency range.

2.2.1.3 Lessons learned from rapid emission checks

This practical exercise demonstrates the viability of rapid emissions checks for early detection of high electromagnetic emission levels produced by PV systems. A reduced procedure inspired by the CISPR 37 draft has been used and found suitable for both magnetic and electric field measurements. The whole campaign was carried out in half a working day, including the time for setting up and putting away all the instrumentation.

This was partly possible because of the advantages of using a compact measurement system for measuring the emissions in the time domain. First, compact USB oscilloscopes are nowadays available even with a 1 GHz bandwidth, more than 5 GSa/s, and very deep memory like 1 GSa, e.g. PicoScope 6000E Series. It is shown that using compact oscilloscopes allows for excellent EMI measurements provided the appropriate software processing. Secondly, this lightweight and small instrument is easy to carry, can be powered directly from the USB port, and is robust to take on-site. Finally, as we worked the scopes as FFT-based measuring receivers, we obtained faster measurement times and full spectrum measurements at once.

In general, oscilloscope affordability is another benefit that should not be neglected for this application. It is well known that high end EMI receivers can be very expensive instruments. Conversely, USB oscilloscopes with acceptable performance can be an order of magnitude less costly. Moreover, if one would like to focus on H-field measurements, where there is a higher risk of strong emissions from PV systems, suitable equipment solutions can be found in the 2 k€ - 3 k€ range.

Concerning source identification, time-domain emissions measurements were also valuable due to the following reason:

- The full spectrum corresponds to a single waveform acquisition. This means that, for every frequency, we have captured the emissions for the same operating conditions: mode, loading, etc. Moreover, the uncertainty due to varying ambient noise in the measurements is reduced.
- Continuous real-time measurements facilitate identifying intermittent or discontinuous disturbances in the ambient level. Transients can be identified easily and eliminated from the measurement if required.
- Faster measurements allow more measurement points in the same time frame. That means, more information to check if a certain frequency is generated by the EUT or not.

Full spectrum QP measurements are available every time at not significant increment in measurement time. This is important because it allows the complete information before applying the corresponding EMI mitigation techniques.

Overall, the work presented here is expected to contribute to the development of new guidelines addressed to PV systems installers, so they can perform the Rapid Emissions Checks mentioned earlier. We consider time-domain EMI measurements to be one option of enabling such tasks, allowing interference problems to be detected and fixed early, before commissioning such fixed installation.

2.2.2 Measurement on three study cases

In this section, we summarise the main results, challenges encountered and experiences with in situ measurements in three well-defined scenarios: a complete photovoltaic (PV) system, an airport passenger boarding bridge and finally, an industrial pallet washing machine.

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2.2.2.1 Measurement procedure

All measurements are performed in open, unshielded environments and under the influence of electromagnetic disturbances of all types: wireless communications, broadcasting, as well as other electronic devices. In order to discern the contribution of the EUT, a measurement is conducted with the equipment switched off (ambient level measurement) and then compared with a measurement with the equipment in operation. Measures are taken at least at 3 points on different axes in order to find the side of the EUT with the most significant emission. According to the CISPR 11 standard, for class A group 1 equipment (all of the studied cases are within this group), the measurement distance is 30m. Nevertheless, the new draft of the CISPR 37 standard allows measurements at 10m. Both distances are considered for later analysis. Additionally, the CISPR 37 draft describes a procedure to define the EUT boundary (Figure 40) when it encompasses different elements, for example, in the case of a photovoltaic system, where there are solar panels and an inverter. This is used to determine the distance from the EUT to the antenna required by the standard.

Figure 40. Boundary determination for a multi-unit EUT according to CISPR 37. The measurement distance is referenced to the boundary outlined with a green dashed line.

The usual frequency range assessed goes from 150 kHz to 30 MHz for magnetic field emissions and from 30 MHz to 1 GHz for electric field emissions. For the magnetic field, a loop antenna in three different axes (x, y, and z) at the height of 2m. For the electric field, a biconical antenna is employed for the range of 30 MHz to 200 MHz and a log-periodic antenna for the 200 MHz to 1 GHz range. Both polarities (vertical and horizontal) are evaluated while maintaining a height of 1m. In the last two cases, the antennas are connected to a 30dB preamplifier to achieve a higher sensitivity.

For the measurement campaigns covered here we used a multi-channel time-domain EMI measurement system compatible with flexible resolution deep memory oscilloscopes to capture and process EMI waveforms. Welch's method is used for spectral estimation, and adaptive windowing functions are used to set any required resolution bandwidth. For H-field emissions, the hardware used was the 4-channels USB oscilloscope model PicoScope 5444B from Pico Technology. It has up to 16bit vertical resolution, 1GSa/s of maximum sampling rate, 200MHz bandwidth, and memory of 512MSa. With this configuration, CISPR 16-1-1 baseline requirements are met for CISPR bands A and B [6], [9]. Conversely, a 4-channel Digital Real-time Oscilloscope Tektronix 5104B was employed for E-field measurements. It has a maximum sampling rate of 10GSa/s and a bandwidth of 1GHz with frequency response correction.

A. Study Case 1: Photovoltaic system

The first case of study is a PV system. This system's constituent elements are a 2kW scaled-down inverter which models a 500kW grid-connected PV inverter, 12 solar panels and AC power sources simulating the AC grid. A provisional outdoor facility is deployed to evaluate the system under natural illumination conditions (Figure 41).

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Figure 41. System under test in the outdoor test site. The photo shows the DC-AC inverter with 12 PV panels behind it.

This experiment was designed to try alternative measurement methodologies, not as an actual test for certifying compliance. The measurements were deployed in a parking lot in Magdeburg, Germany. The wiring and the installation are not meant to be representative of an actual professional one. Sources of electromagnetic disturbances in the surroundings influenced the measurements, in particular, an electric vehicle charger located at 30m from the EUT and a tram stop located approximately at a distance of 70m.

Here the primary interest is to evaluate the magnetic field emissions, which are measured from 9 kHz up to 30MHz. The Picoscope 5444B was used as the measuring device. RF cables, connectors and transitions were transported with the oscilloscope in a hand-carried suitcase. Antennas were provided by the host where the experiments were conducted.

Due to the site constraints, only a few points were defined to evaluate the emissions at different orientations. This subsection presents a couple of relevant cases, showing the functionality of the time domain compact measurement system. In the first example, the magnetic field is measured at a distance of 30m from the equipment (setup in Figure 42).

Figure 42. Setup used for in situ magnetic field measurements for the PV system. Distance to the EUT is 30m.

Keeping the loop antenna (Schwarzbeck FMZB 1513) in the same position, two measurements are conducted, one with the device powered off and one with the device in operation. The H-field's x-, y-, and z- orientations of the magnetic field are considered at every measurement point. The ambient level measurement with the equipment switched off is used to determine the environmental electromagnetic interference of the test site. Results are compared in Figure 43.

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Figure 43. Magnetic field strength measured along the z-axis (Hz) at 30m distance from the EUT.

A rise in received magnetic field intensity is detected when the EUT is turned on. The test had to be repeated several times, as some narrow band components appeared around 80 kHz in some measurements. It turned out this contribution was from the braking and start-up of the tramway in the station close to the test site. However, as measurements were performed in real-time, this situation was identified and solved by repeating fully compliant acquisitions every second.

Additionally, measurements at a 10m distance were taken to obtain a more precise comparison of the contribution of the EUT in relation to the ambient noise levels (Figure 44). This time, a narrow component is seen at $f_0 = 92$ kHz along with its harmonics above 300 kHz. In the previous case, at 30m (Figure 43), the peak at f_0 also appeared but with a smaller magnitude. Note also the higher amplitude of the narrowband disturbance at 138 kHz, which is increased by 20dB. Nevertheless, as this peak appears in the ambient measurements, it does not correspond to the EUT. In other words, we are approaching the unrecognized noise source instead. It is meaningful to perform investigative measurements at closer distances than the standard one in order to identify whether the different spectral components are produced by the EUT, or by unrecognized elements in the surroundings.

Figure 44. Magnetic field strength measured along the x-axis at 10m distance.

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B. Study Case 2: Passenger boarding bridge

The second scenario is a passenger boarding bridge intended for airport use. The test site is the actual facility where it is manufactured before being transported to the end customer. The maximum length of the EUT is 38m and it has several electrical panels, touch screens, controls and motors. The reference point for measuring the distance from the antenna to the EUT is the midpoint between the cockpit and the main movement engine. An image of the EUT with a loop antenna at a distance of 30m is shown in Figure 45.

Figure 45. Photo of the in situ setup for magnetic field emissions measurements from a passenger boarding bridge.

The contribution of the EUT with respect to the ambient noise is noticeable even at 30m, as shown in the 150 kHz - 300 kHz range (Figure 46). Initially, it was assumed this broadband emission was due to the motion system when the passenger boarding bridge performs short translations forward and backwards. Nonetheless, after several repetitions, we observed that such disturbances were not produced in some cases. It was found that while our measurements were run, a group of technicians were working on another passenger boarding bridge. In other words, time-domain measures helped identify fluctuations in ambient noise levels that otherwise may have led to false assumptions. This is why it is essential to perform several to characterize the electromagnetic environment better and provide more confidence regarding the assessment's conclusions. That is, to ensure the disturbances reported are produced by the EUT and not by uncontrolled nearby elements in the surroundings.

Figure 46. Magnetic field strength measured along the x-axis at 30m distance.

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The electric field is measured at a 10m distance in order to achieve a higher signal-to-noise ratio after no significant detection was possible at 30m. In this case, and after repeating several measures in the same working mode, broadband emissions from 40 MHz up to 300 MHz are detected, as depicted in Figure 47.

Figure 47. Electric field emissions measured at 10m distance in horizontal polarization.

C. Study Case 3: Pallet washing tunnel

The last study case is a pallet washing tunnel machine (Figure 48). It consists of a conveyor belt through which the pallets enter to be cleaned and rinsed. The main electrical/electronic elements that can cause interference are the motors (wash and bilge pumps and the drag chain), motor drivers, electric heaters, electro-valves, and an interface display.

Figure 48. A pallet washing tunnel.

The most interesting aspect of this in situ test is the test site itself, an industrial warehouse approximately 54m long and 30m wide, with no other machinery or electronic equipment active during the test. The test site ensures an obstacle-free distance of more than 30m.

An image of the test site with the antenna placed at 30m is shown in Figure 49. To evaluate the different faces of the equipment, the EUT was rotated every 90° with the help of a forklift. At the same time, this was helpful because the measurement axis remained the same.

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Figure 49. Setup used for in situ radiated field emissions measurements from the pallet washing tunnel in an industrial warehouse.

Several measurements are performed at 30m, 10m and 3m. Regarding results obtained at 30m, it was not possible to identify the EUT emissions from the ambient levels, so a shorter distance was used. Then, the antenna is placed at a distance of 10m, and the front face of the EUT is oriented to the front of the antenna. No noticeable variation in the measured spectrum is observed. Nevertheless, when rotating the EUT 90° counterclockwise, the side where the main electronics of the EUT are located, some low-level broadband emission between 200MHz and 300MHz is detected (Figure 50).

Figure 50. E-field emissions measured at 10m distance in horizontal polarization and with the pallet washing tunnel rotated 90° counterclockwise.

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Subsequently, the antenna is placed at 3m from the equipment, maintaining the same measurement axis. It must be noticed that at 3m, the measurements are not in far-field conditions. Therefore, such measurements were only intended to corroborate the source of the emissions was the EUT. Results are illustrated in Figure 51. As expected, there is an increase of magnitude in the broadband emissions registered in the 200 MHz – 300 MHz band and, additionally, the field strength level between 50 MHz and 60 MHz also rises.

Figure 51. E-field emissions at 3m distance in horizontal polarization.

2.2.2.2 Lessons learned from three study cases

Several lessons are drawn based on the experience gained and the different scenarios studied to improve the in situ radiated emissions methodology. Some of them, if not the most relevant to bear in mind, are the following:

- The ambient levels are changing over time. It is highly likely that the two consecutive emission measurements differ substantially due to the time-varying ambient noise. This especially occurs when other equipment in the surroundings are prone to generate disturbances. It is important to identify the different noise sources in the spectrum and to minimize the operation of nearby electronic/electrical devices. For this purpose, FFT-based receivers with real-time capabilities are convenient.
- Due to the relatively high field intensity of broadcasting and communication services in the environment, specific bands will inherently be well above the limits. In such conditions, according to CISPR 11, it is necessary to compare if the field strength in the frequency bands surpassing the limits is increased when the EUT is operating to determine if the EUT complies with the emissions requirement. Beyond that, time domain measurements can be helpful for decomposing broadband from narrowband signals in the time domain thus providing some degree of ambient noise cancellation. Likewise, multichannel time-domain measurement systems facilitate the correlation between conducted, near-field and far-field phenomena, which is key in the emissions investigation process.
- The fast time-domain measurements are advantageous for equipment whose operation mode doesn't allow a continuous cycle. In the passenger boarding bridge, which made 20s motion sequences with a progressive movement, we acquired data corresponding to a given position and state. If the measurement had been made with a spectrum analyzer, each frequency would have been associated with the variable EUT positions and power consumption, thus delivering misleading results.

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- Most of the time, at 30m, the EUT emissions can hardly be discerned from the ambient noise, in particular for *E*-field measurements. At such a distance, it is probable that some disturbances detected are caused by external elements which are closer to the antenna than the EUT itself. Hence, it is necessary to reduce the measurement distance, at least, to check that the magnitude of the detected disturbances increases in relation to the 30m distance and that they are indeed produced by the EUT.

2.2.3 Investigations on CISPR 37 based test sites

2.2.3.1 Site insertion loss (SIL) measurements

Draft CISPR 37 requires validation of test sites for radiated emissions. Site insertion loss (SIL) measurements are defined for both electric and magnetic field in draft CISPR 37. In addition to CISPR 37 provisions, few methods from CISPR 16-1-4 also were applied to SIL measurements, i.e. additional distances [13]. In this regard, three different test sites were selected to investigate. One of these sites is a perfect site which is an antenna calibration site complies with CISPR 16-1-4. This site is named as open area test site (OATS) and has almost a perfect metallic floor with 30m width and 60m length. Second site is another open area in front of the mosque in TUBITAK. Third one is a car park in front of one of the buildings in TUBITAK premises.

2.2.3.1.1 OATS electric field SIL measurements

Electric field SIL measurements were taken at 3m and 10m distances. Antenna positions were 2m horizontal, 1.5m vertical, 1m horizontal and 1m vertical in a. A view of OATS is seen in Figure 52.

Figure 52. Electric field SIL measurements in OATS

Electric field SIL measurements were taken in the frequency range of 30 MHz – 1000 MHz. It is seen that under 300 MHz, deviations from ideal SIL values are higher than that of the upper frequencies from 300 MHz. In figure 53 and Figure 54, 10m and 3m SIL measurements in OATS are given respectively. A peak is seen around 540 MHz, but this peak is common in all test sites and interpreted as a resonance at the measurement setup a deviation resulting from the environment. It is clear that horizontal measurements are much closer to ideal SIL values. That is, reflections are expected at these frequencies regarding the heights of antenna.

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Figure 53. Electric field SIL measurements in OATS @10m

Figure 54. Electric field SIL measurements in OATS @3m

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2.2.3.1.2 Mosque courtyard electric field SIL measurements

Photograph of SIL measurements at mosque courtyard is given in Figure 55.

Figure 55. Electric field SIL measurements in mosque courtyard

Figure 56. Electric field SIL measurements in mosque courtyard @10m

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Figure 57. Electric field SIL measurements in mosque courtyard @10m

Deviations from ideal SIL values at 10m and 3m distance are depicted in Figure 56 and Figure 57 respectively. Similar with the OATS, horizontal SIL values are closer to ideal values than that of the vertical values. Additionally, deviations occur under almost 400 MHz.

2.2.3.1.3 Car park electric field SIL measurements

As the third site, car park was chosen and this area contains more obstacles than the mosque courtyard. Measurement site, results for 10m and 3m are given in Figure 58, Figure 59 and Figure 60 respectively.

Figure 58. Electric field SIL measurements in car park

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Figure 59. Electric field SIL measurements in car park @10m

Figure 60. Electric field SIL measurements in car park @3m

As seen in Figure 59 and Figure 60, deviations from ideal SIL values seem similar to OATS and mosque courtyard except the 30 MHz – 300 MHz range.

2.2.3.1.4 Electric field SIL results

SIL measurements show that horizontal values are closer than the vertical values due to reflections from the ground and surroundings. In the frequency range of 30 MHz – 400 MHz, vertical SIL values present more deviations than the horizontal. Additionally, 3m measurements present better results than 10m measurements.

In conclusion, radiated emission measurements can be performed after a rapid SIL measurement so that the emission results can be presented in a safer way. As mentioned in previous section, it is necessary to perform ambient measurements before the EUT measurements. To perform more accurate SIL measurements, signal power injected to the transmitting antenna should be as high as possible in order to obtain reliable results.

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2.2.3.1.5 OATS magnetic field SIL measurements

SIL measurements were performed in the frequency range of 150 kHz – 30 MHz. Although CISPR 37 defines SIL measurements for magnetic field measurements, no theoretical SIL value is found in the standard. In this context, it makes sense to measure SIL values in three different sites and compare each of them to the OATS SIL values. In this regard, at three distances and at three axes; 3m, 5m and 10m; X, Y and Z axes, magnetic SIL measurements were performed at each site. Figure 61 (a), (b) and (c) represent the differences in respect to OATS. Measurements were at 3m distance at X, Y and Z axis. Figure 62 and Figure 63 represent the 5m and 10m results respectively. In Figure 61, it is seen that SIL deviations from OATS under 1 MHz, are significantly high when compare to 1 MHz – 30 MHz range at all axes.

(a) X axis @3m

(b) Y axis @3m

(c) Z axis @3m

Figure 61. Magnetic field SIL measurements in respect to OATS at 3m at (a) X axis, (b) Y axis (c) Z axis

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(a) X axis @5m

(b) Y axis @5m

(c) Z axis @5m

Figure 62. Magnetic field SIL measurements in respect to OATS at 5m at (a) X axis, (b) Y axis (c) Z axis

Particularly at 10m distance SIL measurement are not consistent and do not represent meaningful values. In this regard, similarly with the electric field measurements, it is recommended to increase the signal power to make the greater than the ambient noise, so the SIL measurements can be more accurate and reliable. Use of preamplifier strongly recommended. SIL measurements at OATS are given in Table 3. Data can be used for comparison purpose.

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Figure 63. Magnetic field SIL measurements in respect to OATS at 10m at (a) X axis, (b) Y axis (c) Z axis

Table 3. Magnetic field SIL measurement results.

Frequency (MHz)	10m factor			5m factor			3m factor		
	X axis	Y axis	Z axis	X axis	Y axis	Z axis	X axis	Y axis	Z axis
0.15	45,74	38,45	54,27	49,42	51,9	54,19	41,03	43,53	45,66
0.3	58,64	52,73	62,18	48,88	52,53	57,82	39,14	42,51	44,7
0.5	60	64,22	68,07	45,56	49,26	55,35	35,16	38,59	41,05
1	56,3	60,65	70,69	41,72	45,92	52,93	31,19	34,83	37,33
3	53,98	61,77	73,83	40,4	45,4	52,13	30	33,94	36,39
7	53,55	57,5	76,96	41,61	48,1	55,01	32,1	37,04	39,28
9.5	53,36	54,53	75,68	42,23	47,34	57,09	33,25	38,2	41,28
12.5	53,56	51,7	74,77	42,83	46,91	59,48	34,39	39,98	43,66
16	53,89	44,48	72,13	43,32	45,62	61,79	35,28	40,83	46,48
22	53,58	45,89	66,68	43,72	41,46	59,3	36,21	38,41	51,72
30	53,25	41,16	59,66	43,74	36,64	51,31	36,64	33,92	47,64

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2.2.3.2 Study on CISPR 37 conversion factors

Proposals for CISPR 37 include defining the reference distance at 10m, the allowance of measurement distances starting from 3m and distance conversion factors (CF) for the H-field emissions limits from 150 kHz to 30MHz.

This section derives and validates a set of distance conversion factors for the H-field emissions limits for frequencies below 30 MHz, which are intended to be proposed for their inclusion in CISPR 37. Even though the lower frequency range defined for limits is 150 kHz, it is decided to broaden such range from 9 kHz for a possible later extension of the limits towards lower frequencies.

The in situ problem, as well as the motivation to find the factor, are formally formulated in Title 2.3.2.1. Then, electromagnetic simulations based on loop-type source are used to evaluate the variation in the amplitude of the H-field components as we move over measurement axes (Title 2.3.2.2). The correctness of the model is checked through two independent experiments carried out in representative locations, showing very good agreement between measurement and simulations (Title 2.3.2.3). Then, an algorithm is developed to extract the H-field strengths normalized to the reference distance. Such a normalized curve is fitted to a piece-wise linear function that becomes the generalized distance conversion factor (Title 2.3.2.4). Finally, a conclusion is made with some final remarks about the prospective of in situ emissions measurement methods and standards.

For an in situ emission test, the measuring antenna is placed at a measuring distance, d_m , from the reference point around the EUT for each measurement axes. Ideally, measures are taken at the reference distance, d_{ref} , the distance at which the emissions limit is defined by the corresponding standard. In most cases, $d_m \neq d_{ref}$ because of restrictions of the perimeter of the test site as shown in Figure 64.

Figure 64. Top view of a typical in situ situation. At the n -th point, measures are conducted at a distance $d_{m,n}$. Some of the axis allow measures at the reference distance, d_{ref} , while others require measuring at different distances.

Measuring emissions at shorter distances might be convenient to identify emission sources. On the other hand, measuring distances larger than reference distance are necessary. For example, in extremely large EUTs (i.e. wind turbines) or when shorter distances are inaccessible (for example, when a road is in the way).

Hence, if $d_m \neq d_{ref}$, conversion factors, $CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$, are needed to set the standard emission limits at a d_{ref} , $L_{ref}(f)$, to the actual measuring distance d_m , as given by,

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$$L_m(f) = L_{ref}(f) + CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f), \quad (1)$$

where $L_m(f)$ is the equivalent limit at d_m . Both limits are expressed in dB μ A/m.

Such conversion factors must consider the variation of field strength with distance and the influence of the orientation of the source. In this specific case and frequency range, the focus is on the emissions in terms of absolute magnetic field strength expressed in decibel units (dB μ A/m). Therefore, conversion factors will depend on the ratio of the field, Δ' , between two arbitrary points P_{ref} and P_m :

$$\Delta'(P_m, P_{ref}, f) = H_m(f) - H_{ref}(f), \quad (2)$$

where H_m and H_{ref} are the field strength levels at points P_m and P_{ref} , respectively. P_m and P_{ref} are determined by the distance with respect to the EUT boundary, the orientation of the measurement axis, and the height of the antenna, h .

Regarding this, the H-field emissions depend on the type of source and change from EUT to EUT. Such emissions can be represented as a combination of fundamental magnetic and electric field sources. Nonetheless, for simplicity, it is decided to use a loop antenna as the source model to calculate the H-field distribution. Previous discussions held at the referenced technical working groups support such a compromise criterion.

Based on the model of a standard 60cm loop antenna [13] proposed in Figure 65, the ratios on x- and y- axes can be derived from (2) and, in Cartesian coordinates, are defined as:

$$\Delta_x(d_m, d_{ref}, f) = H(d_m, 0, h, f) - H(d_{ref}, 0, h, f), \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_y(d_m, d_{ref}, f) = H(0, d_m, h, f) - H(0, d_{ref}, h, f), \quad (4)$$

where $d_{ref} = 10m$ is assumed throughout all the document. As measures are conducted typically in the x-y plane, ratio associated to z-axis is not considered.

$CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$ shall be a single set of factors, that apply to H-field emissions limits independently of the antenna orientation. Therefore, CF must consider both Δ_x and Δ_y . The ratios Δ_x and Δ_y are simulated and validated in Title 2.3.2.2 and 2.3.2.3, respectively. Then, the algorithm to extract the conversion factors is presented in Title 2.3.2.4.

2.2.3.2.2 Simulation

The method of moments is used to compute the electromagnetic field using MATLAB and 4nec2 solvers. The simulation has been performed at 1000 equally log-spaced frequency points from 9 kHz to 30 MHz and at various distances from 3m to 100m.

The simulation model is a circular loop with a diameter of 60cm oriented in x-axis as shown in Figure 65. The source is located at (0, 0, h) and the height from the ground plane to the center of the antenna is $h = 1.3m$. For each condition, the E-field and H-field at a single point are recorded along the x- and y-axis

Figure 66 presents Δ_x and Δ_y for $d_m = 3m$ and Figure 67 shows the results at $d_m = 30m$. The selection of such example distances is not arbitrary. First of all, 3m is selected as the shortest measurement distance typically used during radiated emissions tests in a standard test site. On the other hand, 30m is picked due to the legacy as the distance at which the magnetic field limits are defined [14].

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Figure 65. Simulation model with the defined axis. The ground plane is modelled as an infinite and perfect electric conductor.

It is important to consider that, at such a distance and depending on the equipment type and topology and ambient field level conditions, the EUT emissions might not be detectable.

Figure 66. Ratios obtained in the x- and y-axis for $d_m = 3m$.

Figure 67. Ratios obtained in x- and y-axis for $d_m = 30m$.

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It is observed how, as the frequency increases, the ratios show a transition from near-field to far-field. Such frequency dependence for each distance should be considered when designing the conversion factor extraction algorithm.

2.2.3.2.3 Model validation

The simulation model for Δ_x is validated experimentally throughout two different measurement campaigns that are described in what follows. Considering the intrinsic characteristics of the small loop, the validation of Δ_y in an open area is omitted due to high levels of ambient noise.

A. Experiment 1: 100 kHz - 2MHz

In the first experiment, an R&S HFH2-Z2E broadband active loop antenna is used as the receiving element. For the transmitter, two loops of different sizes are built, one with a dimension of 0.75m x 0.75m and a larger one with a dimension of 1.5m x 1.5m. The center of both loops respect to ground is at 1.3m±5cm and they are located at a distance d_m from the receiver antenna as depicted in Figure 68.

Figure 68. Simplified diagram of Experiment 1 setup.

The receiving antenna has a fixed position to keep an ambient noise level as similar and repetitive as possible during the experiment. An example photo of the experiment is shown in Figure 69.

Figure 69. Experiment 1. The measuring antenna and the 1.5m x 1.5m loop are shown.

In the transmission end, chirp pulses are injected to cover the range from 100 kHz to 2 MHz. In reception, a custom time domain measurement system (emiGO™ by EMC Barcelona) is used, which is based on a general-purpose oscilloscope (Picoscope 5444D MSO) connected to a computer with its own software that calculates the spectrum in compliance with existing standards. The resolution bandwidth is according to CISPR 16. The

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sampling rate is 250MSa/s, the resolution is 12-bit, and the acquisition time is 1s per chirp. Results of the H-field recorded at several distances are displayed in Figure 70.

Figure 70. Recorded magnetic field at different distances in Experiment 1. Ambient noise is depicted as a black trace.

To obtain Δ_x , the field strength level at each distance for $f = 1\text{MHz}$ is recorded and normalized with the field strength level at 10m. Δ_x obtained with two different sizes of transmitting loops are practically equal below 2 MHz.

B. Experiment 2: 1MHz - 30MHz

The purpose of the second experiment is to cover the range from 1MHz up to 30MHz. This time, the transmitting antenna is a passive loop Schwarzbeck HFRA 5149 and the receiver loop is a broadband loop Schwarzbeck FMBZ 1519B. Antenna height (from the center to ground) is 1.3m. Acquisition settings are the same as Experiment 1. A photo of the experiments is shown in Figure 71.

Figure 71. Experiment 2. The open area test site and the transmitting and receiving antennas are depicted.

In this case, ambient levels measured are shown in Figure 72, and frequencies of 1 MHz, 5 MHz, 10 MHz, 20 MHz and

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30 MHz are selected for the experiment. In those frequencies, no emissions from other devices or nearby communication systems were present. A sinusoidal signal of same level was injected to an amplifier connected to the transmitting antenna. For each frequency and distance, the level obtained at the receiving antenna is recorded. Then, H-field levels are normalized to a reference distance of 10m in order to extract the ratios Δ_x .

Figure 72. Experiment 2. Ambient magnetic field noise level.

C. Results

This section presents the results from experimental validation compared with the obtained in the simulation. The Δ_x ratio is compared as a function of distance for five specific frequencies. In Figure 73, the results of Experiment 1, Experiment 2 and simulations at 1 MHz are shown.

The lowest frequency considered is 1 MHz, which is below the corner frequency in all simulated cases. We can see that Experiment 1 fits the simulation excellently, with a small divergence at high distances (higher than 25m). These results allow us to validate the model at this frequency. A larger divergence is seen in the performance of Experiment 2. This may be due to the actual efficiency of using smaller transmission and reception antennas (50cm each). However, such a deviation is in the order of magnitude of tolerable uncertainties in typical EMC tests.

At 5 MHz, 10 MHz, 20 MHz and 30 MHz the results are the obtained from Experiment 2. Comparisons are shown in Figure 74 to Figure 77, respectively.

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Figure 73. Simulation versus experimental results at 1MHz.

Figure 74. Simulation versus experimental results at 5MHz.

Figure 75. Simulation versus experimental results at 10MHz.

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Figure 76. Simulation versus experimental results at 20MHz.

At frequencies from 5 MHz to 20 MHz, a better correspondence is observed. In the upper range of 30 MHz, simulations and experiments overlap from 7m to 30m, but a small discrepancy can be noticed at shorter distances. These effects are due to the practical and real characteristics of the antennas and the equipment and cables used to generate the transmission. However, having validated most of the frequencies and distances, we consider the simulation model to be adequate and consistent with the experiments.

Figure 77. Simulation versus experimental results at 30MHz.

The measurement uncertainty has been estimated for the experimental validation. Since the receiving antenna factor and cable attenuation do not change with the antenna position, the ratio Δ_x in terms of H-field is equivalent to the ratios calculated using the voltage level at the antenna port, V . Therefore, the model of the measurement system, with all quantities in decibel units, is according to (5),

$$V = V_{QP} + \delta_a + \delta_{step} + \delta_d + \delta_h, \tag{5}$$

where V_{QP} is the voltage level detected using the FFT-based measuring receiver in quasi-peak (QP) mode, and its variations represent the measurement repetitiveness; δ_a corresponds to the sine wave voltage level tolerances of the instrument in the given frequency range, δ_{step} is the error due to a limited frequency resolution of the spectrum, and δ_d and δ_h are the readings variation due to imprecise antenna positioning in the horizontal and vertical plane.

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Table 4 presents the uncertainty budget for V , indicating the type of evaluation used for each contribution, their estimated value and the probability distribution assigned to each. In this case, all uncertainty contributions are considered independent, and their mean values are 0dB. The standard uncertainties are combined directly in decibel units following the guidelines in CISPR 16-4-2 [10]. This approximation is deemed acceptable when the values are small in order to avoid asymmetrical intervals for the combined uncertainty.

Table 4. Uncertainty budget for the measurement of the received voltage.

Contribution factors		Standard deviation	Probability distribution		Standard uncertainty	Unit
Type	Source of uncertainty		Function	Divisor		
A	Receiver reading, V_{QP}	0,20	Normal ($k=1$)	1,00	0,20	dB
B	Level accuracy, δ_a	0,50	Normal ($k=2$)	2,00	0,25	dB
B	Freq. resolution, δ_{step}	0,37	Rectangular	1,73	0,21	dB
B	Antenna distance, δ_d	0,40	Rectangular	1,73	0,23	dB
B	Antenna height, δ_h	0,10	Rectangular	1,73	0,06	dB
Combined standard uncertainty =					$\pm 0,45$	dB
Expanded uncertainty ~95 % ($k=2$) =					$\pm 0,90$	dB

Concerning the evaluation of the uncertainty, for Type A sources, we performed multiple repetitions of the measurement, and the standard deviation was calculated with degrees of freedom equal to 29. The Type B sources related to the instrument are evaluated using information from calibration certificates, while those regarding the antenna position are estimated using simulation.

Finally, given the measured field ratios require two voltage measurements, then the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of Δ_x is estimated in ± 1.3 dB.

2.2.3.2.4 Conversion factors

In this section, a conversion factor based on the obtained ratios Δ_x and Δ_y will be proposed. Firstly, we address the problem of combining Δ_x and Δ_y in such a way we can extract a single ratio, Δ_c . Then, straightforward procedure is presented in order to convert Δ_c to final piece-wise conversion factors, CF. Such procedure is necessary in order to simplify the implementation of factors in corresponding standards. Finally, CF for several distances are summarized in form of a table. Note that Δ_c and CF will depend on d_m , d_{ref} , and f .

A. Combination of Δ_x and Δ_y

In a real situation, the orientation of the source with respect to the measurement axis is unknown, as well as the direction of the maximum emissions. This should be considered when combining Δ_x and Δ_y in order to prevent an unintended relaxation of the emission requirements after the application of the conversion factors. This is important because the level of protection to radio services should be guaranteed.

To analyze this phenomenon, the magnetic field obtained around a small loop source at a hypothetical distance of 10m (reference distance) is simulated (Figure 78) for a single frequency. In other words, the magnetic field is sensed around the EUT and the field strength is plotted as a function of the measurement axis azimuth angle, being 0° the orientation of the maximum amplitude. Then, a hypothetical limit is set at the median value of the field strength in order to have 50% of measurement points that exceed the limit and 50% of measurement points that are below. From another point of view, if we take a single measurement on a random axis, we would have the same probability of determining whether the equipment is compliant or non-compliant.

Then, it is considered that it is not possible to measure at the reference distance set by the limit, 10m, so the measurements are conducted at, for example, $d_m = 3$ m. Consequently, the limit has to be corrected by applying

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some conversion factors, CF. Let us assume that $CF = \Delta_C$. Figure 79 shows the corrected limit calculated according the two definitions of Δ_C listed below:

$\Delta_{C1} = \Delta_x$, because the x component is dominant when the source is an elemental magnetic loop, as shown in Figure 63.

$\Delta_{C2} = \min(\Delta_x, \Delta_y)$, considering the dominant component of the H-field vector is unknown.

Figure 78. H-field strength around a small loop source at 10m from its center and 1.3 m height. The median of the field strength is used as a hypothetical emissions limit. Therefore, if a single measurement axis randomly selected over the EUT plane, probability that the EUT emissions are found to be above the limit is 50%.

Figure 79. H-field strength around a small loop source above a ground plane at 3m from its center and 1.3m height. The limit is used at 10m in Figure 78 is converted to the measurement distance using Δ_{C1} and Δ_{C2}

After applying the conversion factors according to the first definition (Δ_{C1}), only 23.52% of the points at 3m are above the limit, which signifies a higher risk of not detecting that the emissions are exceeding the limit with respect to the original case. Using Δ_{C2} , 90.28% of possible points around the EUT exceed the limit. From the previous results, it is clear that approach (2) provides protections level that are more likely to deliver the correct conclusions of the emission test.

This analysis has been extended in terms of frequency and distances, assuming that the reference distance, d_{ref} , is 10m, where the probability is 50%. In other words, the former simulation has been repeated for the whole frequency range under study and distances from 3m to 10m. Then, the probability of exceeding the limit is represented. The results applying Δ_{C1} and Δ_{C2} are shown in Figure 80 and Figure 81 respectively.

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The straight green line at 10m for all frequencies is where no conversion factors are applied, and it indicates a probability of 50%. In Figure 80, it is confirmed that an incorrect definition of the conversion factor may lead to a significant relaxation of the emissions requirement, which is not desirable. On the other hand, in the case of Figure 81, applying the conversion factors increases the likelihood of detecting that the EUT emissions are above the applicable limit.

Therefore, it is proposed to define as,

$$\Delta_C = \min(\Delta_X, \Delta_Y). \quad (6)$$

Nonetheless, there should be a symmetry between the factors applied when approaching the source or when departing from the source. That means the dependence of Δ_C on d_m , d_{ref} and f as $\Delta_C(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$ must satisfy the condition,

$$\Delta_C(d_1, d_2, f) = -\Delta_C(d_2, d_1, f), \quad (7)$$

where d_1 and d_2 are arbitrary distances. To fulfill this requirement, the final Δ_C is defined as,

$$\Delta_C = \text{sgn}(\Delta_X) \min(|\Delta_X|, |\Delta_Y|). \quad (8)$$

B. Piece-wise factor extraction

The conversion factor at a given distance d_m , $CF(d_m, d_{ref}, f)$, must be straightforward to apply, as well as allow a feasible integration into the standards. Thus, the function that describes the factor, which will be dependent on distance and frequency, must be expressed as simply as possible. Therefore, it is proposed to approximate Δ_C through a combination of piece-wise linear functions, $CF_i(f)$ as shown in (9). For sake of simplicity, the dependence of d_m and d_{ref} is omitted in the notation.

$$CF(f) = \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} CF_i(f), \quad (9)$$

where $CF_i(f)$ is the equation of a straight line defined between a pair of changepoints occurring at discrete frequencies φ_{i-1} and φ_i . In other words,

$$CF_i(f) = \begin{cases} \alpha_i f + \beta_i & \text{for } \varphi_{i-1} < f \leq \varphi_i \\ 0 & \text{for } f \leq \varphi_{i-1} \vee f > \varphi_i \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

To extract φ_i , changepoint analysis is carried out following the methodology in [16]. This involves identifying points within a dataset where specific statistical properties change. These properties can include the standard deviation, the root mean square (RMS) level, the mean value, or the slope.

Assuming each section of the conversion factors is represented by an ordered sequence of sampled data points $\Delta_{C,1:n} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$, each point corresponding to the frequencies $F_{1:n} = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$, and that it is of interest to fit $(f_{1:n}; \Delta_{C,1:n})$ according to the model in (9) and (10) for $k + 1$ piece-wise linear segments. This requires to find k optimal changepoints, $cp_{1:k}$, each of them must be calculated to segment the dataset according to abrupt changes in the mean value and slope. These changepoints occur at discrete frequencies $\varphi_{1:k} = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_k\}$. Each changepoint discrete frequency corresponds to a vector position that is an integer between 1 and $n - 1$ inclusive.

We define $\varphi_0 = f_1$ and $\varphi_{k+1} = f_n$ and assume that the changepoints are ordered such that $\varphi_i < \varphi_j$ if, and only if, $i < j$. Consequently, the k changepoints will split the dataset into $k+1$ segments, with the i -th segment containing $P_{(\varphi_{i-1}); \varphi_i}$.

One commonly used approach to identify multiple changepoints is to minimize (11),

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$$\sum_{i=1}^{k+1} [\kappa_i (\Delta_{C,(\varphi_{i-1});\varphi_i})] + g(k) \quad (11)$$

where $\kappa_i(\cdot)$ is the cost function for the i -th segment and $g(k)$ is a penalty to guard against overfitting. For linear cost functions, the PELT (Pruned Exact Linear Time) method is computationally efficient for finding the changepoints. More about the PELT method and other algorithms for solving the previous equation are reviewed in [16].

Regarding the cost

function in (11), a suitable choice is the sum of squared errors, SSE , as it measures the goodness of fit of regression models. The SSE of the i -th segment is given by,

$$SSE_i = \sum_{j=1}^m (a_{j,i} - CF_i(f_{j,i}))^2 \quad (12)$$

where $(f_{j,i}, a_{j,i})$ is the frequency-amplitude coordinate of the j -th point of the i -th segment, with that segment containing m samples. A small SSE indicates a tight fit of the model to the data.

Then, the best linear fit of the subset of m points in the i -th segment $\Delta_{C,(\varphi_{i-1});\varphi_i}$ is obtained through the least squares regression, that is,

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m (\bar{a}_i - a_{j,i}) (\bar{f}_i - f_{j,i})}{\sum_{j=1}^m (\bar{f}_i - f_{j,i})^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\beta_i = \bar{a}_i - \alpha_i \bar{f}_i, \quad (14)$$

where α_i and β_i are the slope coefficient and the intercept of the i -th segment in (10), respectively, and \bar{a}_i and \bar{f}_i are the mean values of the amplitudes and their corresponding frequencies, respectively.

Therefore, a piecewise factor for $k = 2$ (3 sections) is calculated employing the former algorithm implemented through the *findchangepts* [17], [18] MATLAB function. In this particular case, $\varphi_0 = 9\text{kHz}$, $\varphi_3 = 30\text{MHz}$ and φ_1 and φ_2 are the variable corner frequencies that depend on d_m . Figure 80 and Figure 81 show examples of the algorithm output for $d_m = 3\text{m}$ and $d_m = 30\text{m}$, respectively.

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Figure 80. Output of the piece-wise factor extraction algorithm. $d_m=3m$.

Figure 81. Output of the piece-wise factor extraction algorithm. $d_m=30m$.

The approximation error, defined as the difference between Δ_c and CF , is calculated for the full range of frequencies and distances from 3 m to 100 m. The distribution of such error is presented as a histogram (Figure 82). It is found that for 70% of the points, the error is within ± 0.5 dB while for 95% of cases, the error is better than ± 3 dB and finally, for 99.8% of the points the error is kept less than ± 6 dB.

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Figure 82. Approximation error of the linear piece-wise factors.

C. Results

Distance conversion factors assuming a $d_{ref} = 10m$ are presented on Table 5 and on Figure 83. For the interpretation of the conversion factors proposed, it is important to realize that a positive value means the emissions limit increases as we approach the source. Conversely, negative values indicate the limit decreases as we move further away from the EUT.

Table 5. Distance conversion factors for in situ H-field emissions measurements. The reference distance is 10m. The range of measurement distances is from 3m to 100m.

Measurement distance m	Corner frequency φ_1 MHz	Corner frequency φ_2 MHz	Extrapolation factor (dB)		
			9 kHz to φ_1	φ_1 to φ_2	φ_2 to 30 MHz
3	3.7	11.3	26.8	48.0 – 37.3 log(f)	8.6
4	3.3	9.5	20.5	36.3 – 30.4 log(f)	6.6
5	3.0	8.2	15.5	26.9 – 23.8 log(f)	5.0
6	2.8	7.4	11.4	19.4 – 18.0 log(f)	3.8
7	2.6	6.8	7.9	13.2 – 12.6 log(f)	2.6
8	2.4	6.4	4.9	7.9 – 7.8 log(f)	1.7
9	2.3	6.0	2.3	3.7 – 3.7 log(f)	0.8
15	1.9	4.6	-10.3	-15.3 + 18.4 log(f)	-3.2
20	1.6	4.2	-17.7	-23.8 + 29.4 log(f)	-5.6
25	1.5	3.9	-23.4	-29.5 + 37.4 log(f)	-7.5
30	1.4	3.7	-28.1	-34.0 + 43.9 log(f)	-9.1
50	1.3	3.5	-41.0	-49.8 + 67.4 log(f)	-13.5
70	1.0	3.2	-49.7	-50.6 + 67.1 log(f)	-16.5
100	0.8	3.0	-58.8	-51.4 + 65.9 log(f)	-19.8

In the frequency range φ_1 to φ_2 the correction factor is calculated using the provided formula, where f is the frequency in MHz. Function log is defined as logarithm function in base-10.

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Figure 83. Distance conversion factors for in-situ H-field emissions tests in the frequency range from 9 kHz – 30 MHz.

2.2.3.2.4 Conclusions

Distance conversion factors are obtained for magnetic field limits in the range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz. These factors are experimentally validated with very good agreement throughout the frequency range considered.

A reference distance of 10 m is proposed instead of the historically used one of 30 m. The measurement of magnetic field at shorter distances, especially when the tests are conducted in situ, is advantageous as it allows the detection of the emissions of the EUT with higher field strengths with respect to typical ambient noise levels. However, it is also necessary to provide factors at larger distances in cases where the equipment is very large or consists of many modules. It is also important to provide factors at shorter distances in the case that, due to test site limitations, it is not possible to measure at the distance required by the standard.

A mathematical algorithm was designed to automate the extraction of the said conversion factors and to provide a piece-wise function that allows the factors to be applied in a simple and practical way.

Finally, it is important to consider the proposed factor definition does not relax the current radio protection requirements set by the CISPR. However, after the application of the proposed limits, when assessing an equipment at $d_m < d_{ref}$, the converted limits might be more restrictive at some frequencies with respect to a situation when measuring at $d_m > d_{ref}$. This should be understood when using distance conversion factors as part of the emissions compliance assessment.

2.3 Time domain technique for fast electrical and magnetic radiated emission testing to capture worst case emissions and short duration/transient interference

Most influential inconvenience during in-situ radiated emissions assessments is the effect of uncontrollable and unpredictable ambient noise conditions. Therefore, detecting disturbances produced by the equipment under test (EUT) can be complicated in harsh electromagnetic environments. To reach a meaningful test conclusion, it is crucial to distinguish between both ambient field levels and the EUT emissions. Of course, this is even more cumbersome if we consider a large number of test points (different antenna polarization, multiple measurement axis and distances, etc.), conditions and operating modes that must be included in the test plan. All this implies lengthy and costly test campaigns.

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To answer the current need for practical and reliable radiated emissions measurements in the in-situ context, in this work, we present different strategies. These strategies take advantage of time-domain measurement systems to provide conclusive EMI assessments even in harsh electromagnetic environments.

This section is structured as follows: Title 2.3.1 describes the main challenges of in-situ radiated emissions measures as well as how to determine whether or not an EUT is compliant. Title 2.3.2 presents an introduction to the range of possibilities offered by EMI measurement systems in the time domain and the methodology, measurement procedure, and practical considerations when performing in-situ campaigns. Subsequently, Section Title 2.3.3 discusses five strategies to enhance the distinction between ambient noise and EUT emissions. Then, Title 2.3.4 covers a real application for the in-situ radiated emissions measurements of a PV inverter. Finally, Section 2.3.5 concludes with a brief review of the lessons learned and how they could be applied to future standards for in-situ measurements.

Figure 84. Example radiated emissions measure to illustrate the EUT compliance casuistry. It compares the ambient noise emissions (blue color) along with the measure obtained with the EUT active (green color).

2.3.1 Electric field emissions testing in harsh environments

The CISPR 11 [14] standard has been widely applied for in-situ EMC assessments of industrial, scientific, and medical equipment, as it includes some clauses about this topic. However, this standard only provides limits and minimum number of antenna positions. CISPR 11 refers to CISPR 16-2-3 [19], which provides measurement requirements and, on its Annex A, limited guidance to deal with the high levels of ambient noise. Nonetheless, no former EMC standard is sufficient to eliminate the impact of ambient noise from in-situ measurements.

To address the problem of radiated emissions measurement in harsh electromagnetic environment conditions, let us start by formally describing the problem considering the hypothetical ambient noise spectrum profile as shown in Figure 84.

In such a hypothetical scenario, several distinct situations can be observed depending on the relationship between EUT emissions, $E(f_i)$, and ambient noise, $N(f_i)$, at each i -th frequency, f_i , with respect to the corresponding limits, $L(f_i)$, with a certain margin, $M = 6\text{dB}$. In summary, we can reduce the problem according to the flowchart in Figure 85.

This decision tree should be applied for each frequency in the measured range. Once non-compliance has been detected, this is sufficient to consider that the EUT has failed. In cases when EUT does not fail at f_i , the

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next frequency, f_{i+1} , shall be evaluated. If the compliance is uncertain at some frequency, specific methodologies or strategies to determine the conformity must be employed.

Figure 85. Decision flowchart to assess compliance of an EUT at each frequency f_i . $N(f_i)$ and $E(f_i)$ refer to the magnitude value at f_i for the measure of ambient noise and the measure with the EUT on, respectively. $L(f_i)$ refers to the limit value at f_i . $M = 6$ dB refers to the margin below the limit.

For example, previous research has tackled this problem through ambient noise cancelation methods [20-23]. The cited studies involve complex mathematics and processing algorithms, which are not feasible for a standard test method because explaining them in generalized and plain terms is impossible. In title 2.3.3, we present some techniques for assessing radiated emission measurements when compliance is uncertain due to high ambient noise. These techniques include pre-scanning, which has previously been used in EMI assessment in laboratories, and other new signal processing techniques that are only possible due to employing time-domain analysis.

2.3.2 Measurement method

2.3.2.1 Multi-RBW analysis

In this experiment (Figure 86), the analysis with multiple resolution bandwidth (RBW) is described. By reducing the RBW, we can differentiate narrow bands produced by the EUT that remain overlapped when the normative RBW is applied. The experiment carried out consists of an antenna transmitting a tone at 100.2MHz. The antenna is placed inside an anechoic chamber of a standard EMC laboratory. A receiving antenna of similar characteristics is placed and the door of the chamber is left open in order to have an uncontrollable ambient noise. Note that the generated tone is masked by the FM radio broadcasting services.

A measurement is made with the tone active, another with the tone off, and finally one with the tone active but with the door closed in order to eliminate the ambient noise (Figure 87). The spectrum is computed using a $RBW_1 = 120$ kHz, the bandwidth established in the CISPR16-1-1 standard. At first glance, no difference is observed between the case with the equipment active and the equipment off.

If we recalculate the spectrum using a smaller $RBW_2 = 5$ kHz, a clear difference can be appreciated between a radio station centered at 100MHz and the tone at 100.2MHz generated by our "EUT" (Figure 88).

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Figure 86. Diagram of the test setup employed. An arbitrary generator injects a sinewave signal of 100.2 MHz into a TX antenna, simulating an EUT. The door of the anechoic chamber is left open in order to provide an uncontrollable environment inside the room.

Figure 87. Comparison between three different cases: ambient measurement with generator off, ambient measurement with generator on, and measurement with generator on and anechoic chamber door closed.

Figure 88. Zoom of the case in Figure 87 at 100.2 MHz. It is shown the case with $RBW_1 = 120$ kHz (normative) and with the recalculated spectrum using $RBW_2 = 5$ kHz.

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In contrast, using the normative *RBW*, we are unable to discriminate between the two interferences (black-dashed line). Furthermore, it should be emphasized that, when recalculating the spectrum with the smaller *RBW*, the measure with ambient noise and the measure with the door closed match perfectly.

This experiment is feasible thanks to keeping the data in the time domain. This allows to compute the spectrum for the same capture varying any desired parameter, including the resolution bandwidth. Although a measurement at a lower *RBW* could be performed with a traditional receiver, it would be too time consuming. Furthermore, the verification measure at a lower *RBW* and the measure at a standard *RBW* would correspond to two different realizations, whereby the environmental noises or other conditions could have changed.

2.3.2.2 Time gating

The third experiment consists of eliminating transients in the ambient noise using time gating of impulsive components. Time gating consists of applying a rectangular windows via software to the useful time-domain data and then recomputing the spectrum. It is useful for eliminating high-spikes in the measurement waveforms due to sporadic events not correlated with the EUT operation. Such events may not be present in the measures with the EUT off but may be present in the measures with the active EUT; hence, we are interested in removing them. To support this approach, two different experiments are carried out.

1) Experiment A

The setup of this experiment is shown in Figure 89. It is performed in an anechoic chamber with no external ambient noise, except that an electrical fast transient generator is placed inside, which triggers every 1s. Due to the high rise/fall of the transients, multiple wide bands with high levels appears on the spectrum, overlapping all the useful information from the EUT.

Figure 89. Diagram of the test setup employed. An arbitrary generator injects a sinewave signal of 60 MHz into a TX antenna, simulating an EUT. The anechoic chamber door is closed and a burst/transient voltage generator is placed inside the room.

The acquired waveform in the time domain is depicted in Figure 90. Notice that a transient appears at $t = 310\mu\text{s}$. In our particular case, we are interested in excluding this section of the data, so the spectrum is recomputed by applying a window between $t = 500\mu\text{s}$ and $t = 1\text{ms}$, in which no transient event occurs.

Figure 91 shows the spectrum calculated by taking all the data and the spectrum computed with the gated time-domain window. In addition, a measure was performed with no transient generator in order to get a purely real measure of the EUT.

Two clear conclusions can be drawn from the figure presented. The first one is that the calculated spectrum using the gated time window and the spectrum of the measurement only with the EUT match perfectly. The second one is that the fact of a transient appearing during the dwell time results in a nonclean spectrum with a high level which can easily exceed the limit and mislead to wrong conclusions if we cannot distinguish it from the EUT emissions.

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Figure 90. Time-domain plot of the acquired waveform. Observe a burst transient around $t = 310 \mu\text{s}$. The first part of the signal is excluded and the spectrum is recomputed using only the part highlighted in red.

Figure 91. Comparison of three cases: one with the spectrum computed using the entire measurement time, one with the spectrum computed taking the gated time and finally, a measurement conducted under ideal conditions with no external disturbances.

2) Experiment B

In the second experiment, we evaluate a more realistic case. As EUT, we consider a switched-mode power supply (SMPS) located in an open room (Figure 92).

Nearby, there is an apparatus that randomly produces sporadic transients, which yield to a spectrum with a very high level. In this case, we observe when performing several measurements that the spectrum varies due to this external device. Using the spectrogram (Figure 93), we are able to notice the appearance of different transients up to three different times ($t_1 = 25\text{ms}$, $t_1 = 26.5\text{ms}$, and $t_1 = 93\text{ms}$).

The spectrum is recalculated with a time window from $t = 35\text{ms}$ to $t = 85\text{ms}$. Three cases are shown in Figure 94.

First, the spectrum with the original time-domain data (green plot). In this chart, a very high level spectrum with little information can be visualized. Then, the spectrum with the time gated (orange graph), in which the emission produced by the SMPS is clearly visible and which practically matches with the laboratory measurement of the same EUT. Finally, an ambient measurement without the SMPS and at a moment when the external equipment was not producing transients (blue plot).

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Figure 92. Diagram of the test setup employed. A switching power supply (SMPS) is used as EUT in an open environment. A device producing transients when turning on is present on the test site.

Figure 93. Spectrogram of the measurement performed with the EUT as well as with the external equipment producing disturbances. Note the appearance of sporadic transients at 25, 26.5, and 93 ms.

Figure 94. Comparison of three cases: original spectrum, spectrum calculated with the gated time domain, and finally an ambient measurement with no EUT and no external disturbances.

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2.3.2.3 Time decomposition

This experiment is based on the premise of prior knowledge of the operation of the EUT. In this case, the same SMPS as in the previous experiments is used, which produces impulsive components due to the internal switching of the power transistor. The power supply is placed in a noncontrollable environment (Figure 95) and the measurements are performed.

We automatically retrieve the impulsive part from the time-domain data (Figure 96) exclusively. The rest of the data is set to 0V and then the spectrum is recomputed. Figure 97 shows a zoom of one of the impulsive components produced.

Figure 95. Diagram of the setup used. An SMPS is used as EUT. The door of the anechoic chamber is left open in order to have an uncontrollable environment.

Figure 96. EMI measurement in the time domain. The red trace shows the decomposed waveform taking into account only the impulsive components coming from the EUT.

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Figure 97. Zoom of the measurement in Figure 96 on one of the impulsive events. The nonimpulsive part is set to a voltage of 0 V.

Figure 98. Radiated emissions from the SMPS. Green trace shows the spectrum calculated using the whole acquisition. The blue trace shows the spectrum of the broadband mode produced by impulsive components in waveform.

The spectrum obtained is compared in both measurements in Figure 98 spectrum computed with the original time-domain data and then with the purely impulsive part.

The clear contribution of SMPS is observed while the stationary part of ambient noise (mainly FM broadcasting) is cancelled. This technique is especially useful to eliminate the stationary ambient noise in equipment with a pulse repetition frequency (PRF) lower than the RBW used.

2.3.2.4 Amplitude probability distribution analysis

In the last criterion, a transmitting antenna is placed inside an anechoic chamber with the door open (Figure 99). In previous experiments, a 100.2 MHz tone was injected. However, this time a 100 MHz tone will be generated, which coincides exactly with the carrier frequency of an FM radio station.

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When the measurements are performed, the spectrum is identical either with the signal generator ON or OFF (only ambient noise). Even using criterion B (RBW reduction), it is not possible to discern the injected tone from the ambient noise. However, the field amplitude distribution represented as a probability density function (pdf) is useful for differentiating pure ambient noise levels from the situation where there are significant emissions that are completely overlapped in both time and frequency domains. In order to estimate the pdf, the spectrogram is computed for an acquisition time of $t = 100\text{ms}$. The distribution of the different values of the spectrum at the study frequency, $f_c = 100\text{MHz}$, are shown, as well as the expected value of the measuring detectors. If the complete spectrum is identical in the ambient measure and in the EUT measure, but the amplitude distribution is different, that means that the EUT is producing some disturbance in that specified frequency. Figure 100 shows the results from the ambient noise measure and the measure with the EUT active.

As expected, both distributions differs. This means that the EUT is producing emissions at $f_c = 100\text{MHz}$, which could not be observed directly in the spectrum.

Figure 99. Diagram of the test setup employed. An arbitrary generator feeds a sine wave at 100 MHz into a TX antenna, simulating an EUT. The anechoic chamber door is left open to have an uncontrollable environment inside. There is exactly one radio station broadcasting at $f_c = 100\text{MHz}$.

Figure 100. Study of the amplitude pdf and different associated detectors. Comparison between the ambient measurement with the equipment off and with the equipment on.

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2.3.3 Time-domain magnetic field emission

2.3.3.1 Multi-axis shielded loop antenna

Shielded loop antennas (SLA) are used in magnetic field emission tests. However, the use of a single SLA significantly increases the measurement time, as the procedure requires to measure EUT from four measurement positions in a several antennas orientations to it [2]. To address the issue of using a single SLA in the measurement procedure, an optimization approach was explored by integrating a Multi-axis Shielded Loop Antenna (MSLA) capable of evaluating all required antenna orientations from the single measurement position simultaneously [27].

The design of this antenna is shown in Figure 101. The integration of an MSLA with a multichannel digitizer has demonstrated a high correlation in measurement results when compared to a single SLA with a conventional super-heterodyne receivers [27]. Nonetheless, research has highlighted that measurement results may deviate due to the mutual coupling (MC) effect of the MSLA construction, requiring considerations to resolve differences between the standard SLA and the MSLA configuration [28]. To counteract this effect, investigating the correction factor technique for MC is necessary.

Figure 101. Multi-axis shielded loop antenna.

A. MSLA Construction

The MSLA construction used in this study is depicted in Figure 101. This construction consists of three SLAs nested within each other. To combine them, diameters of 57 cm ($MSLA_y$), 60 cm ($MSLA_x$), and 63 cm ($MSLA_z$) for the SLAs were selected. This antenna construction ensures the alignment of the central point of all loops and removes any offset that could occur if all antennas had the same diameter. Each loop is detachable, which allows to characterize their AF both individually and as a whole MSLA construction itself. The orthogonal orientations of the antennas maximize the cross-polarization isolation [29], [30], yet does not entirely eliminate the coupling due to their physical imperfections effected in any construction of this kind. Figure 102 shows the round mold for antennas building process.

This round mold can be adjusted for any required antenna diameter. Within this round mold, 12 mm wrapped insulated copper tube was positioned to create a circle. A copper T-piece was inserted to create an exit from

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the loop for the copper wire, which will be fed inside the tube. After soldering the inner conductor wire can be installed. Choosing a 60 cm diameter loop antenna provides a practical balance between size and performance: it remains electrically small (well within 1/5 of the 30 MHz), stays below its self-resonance in the frequency range of interest, and provides a higher sensitivity for the low-frequency range. It is also important to note that SLA is highly sensitive to the angle of the magnetic field lines that are crossing its effective area. Rotating the antennas by 90° relative to each other is a straight forward and effective strategy to reduce interference between MSLA and to meet the standards requirement for evaluating three planes from a single antenna position [2]. In Table 6, the physical properties of the MSLA are shown.

Figure 102. Round mold for antenna building process

Table 6. Multi-axis shielded loop antenna construction specification

Antenna diameter (cm)	Inner conductor length (cm)	Area (cm ²)	Air gap in shield (mm)	Outer diameter of the tube (mm)	Inner diameter of the tube (mm)	Tube wall thickness (mm)
57	180	2551	4	12	10	1
60	189	2827	4	12	10	1
63	199	3117	4	12	10	1

B. AF Measurements

To investigate the influence on the AF, the MSLA was deconstructed, and individual antenna AF measurements were performed [31]. These measurements serve as a reference to show deviations in AF between individual antennas and when they are assembled into the MSLA construction. In this study, a traceable loop antenna calibration method using a vector-network analyzer was implemented to calibrate the antennas [32]. The three-loop antenna calibration method, as in [33], requires three individual loop antennas, which are measured in a specific order to calculate the AF for each. To avoid the influence of human error during the measurement procedure, two additional SLAs with a 60 cm diameter were used as reference antennas. Over all measurements the difference in the AFs for the reference antennas did not exceed a

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deviation of 0.05 dB. Because of this the difference in the AF for individual antenna from MSLA and an assembled MSLA construction is caused solely by its construction.

Figure 103 represents the measurement procedure for one disassembled SLA used for X-axis measurements in the MSLA construction. The same procedure was repeated for each antenna after assembling the MSLA. Figure 104 shows one of the three measurements for the MSLA_Y antenna.

Figure 103. Three-antennas calibration setup for a single antenna from the MSLA construction. In this case demonstrated for the antenna which is responsible for the X-axis in the MSLA.

The distance between the centres of the antennas was 1 m, and the distance between the ground and the antenna centre was 1.3 m. This distance between the antennas was used to minimize the influence of the conducting walls in the chamber, where the distance to the walls should be twice the distance between the antennas.

Figure 104. Three-antennas calibration setup for the MSLA. The measurement for the Y antenna in the MSLA.

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C. Measurement Results

The AF for the single antennas and assembled MSLA construction are shown in Figure 105. The AF differences for individual antennas and the MSLA configuration, shown in Figure 106, fall within the range of -0.1 to 0.45 dB. From these results, it can be concluded that the influence of the MSLA on the axial magnetic field component response is low. However, as shown in [6], the measurement error can increase significantly for the response of the nondominant antennas that are influenced by the radial magnetic field component. This occurs for several reasons, such as the antenna construction locally disturbing the field due to imperfect alignment of loops and scattering effects. In the next section, this is shown as MC between antennas.

Figure 105. AF for each antenna in MSLA and SLA construction.

Figure 106. Difference in the AF between SLA and MSLA.

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2.3.3.2 MSLA MC Measurements

In this section, the measurement technique for MC between antennas in the MSLA, along with the measurement results, are introduced.

A. MSLA MC Measurement Method

The MC is expressed here as the S21 parameter measured by the VNA, as shown in Figure 107. The antenna not connected to the VNA was loaded with 50 Ω to maintain its loading conditions as if it were connected to a receiver. Due to the fact that only MSLA will be used further in the formulas and graphs to reduce complexity, “MSLA_X” will be referred to as “X,” “MSLA_Y” as “Y,” and “MSLA_Z” as “Z,” as shown in Figure 107. Measurements of the combinations between antennas X&Y, X&Z, Y&Z in an MSLA construction give the results of the re-radiation magnetic field, which will occur during the actual measurements.

Figure 107. S21 measurement setup for a MSLA construction.

B. MSLA MC Measurement Results

Measurement results show that the MC between each antenna in the proposed MSLA construction with different antenna diameters is relatively low, as visualized in Figures 108(a) and 109(a). The linear scale for the figures was chosen due to the fact that the MC is dominant at the higher frequencies. The highest measured MC was at a frequency of 30 MHz, reaching around -37 dB. The difference of the MC measurement results between Figures 108 and 109 is caused by deconstruction and assembling antenna again. Even if the antenna was assembled in the same way as it was before the MC between antennas can change, since even a small deviation in the antennas placements will result in a, very small, different MC.

The phase relation from the S21 parameter between antennas is shown in Figure 108 (b) and Figure 109 (b). Further, the measured phase shift and the level of the coupled signal will be used for the MC correction factor implementation. Due to this, in Section 2.3.3.3, the MC coefficients will be presented by the $k_{XY}(f)$ factor which is taken from the S21 measurements and represent the amplitude scaling factor from one antenna to another antenna and the phase shift of the coupled signal with respect to the injected signal. Each frequency step from 150 kHz to 30 MHz has its own k coefficient.

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Figure 108. MC measurement results a) amplitude and b) phase behaviour.

Figure 109. MC measurement results a) amplitude and b) phase behaviour.

2.3.3.3 MC Correction factor

In this section the numerical approach for the MC correction factor and the implementation of it are shown.

A. Numerical approach

By implementing a multi-channel digitizer the amplitude and the phase difference between each antenna in MSLA simultaneous measured over the time. When a short-time FFT is applied to the digitized time-domain signals during post-processing, both the amplitude and phase of each frequency component can be accurately tracked as functions of frequency (f) and time (τ). In this work, the MC coefficients $k_{XY}(f)$, $k_{XZ}(f)$ and $k_{YZ}(f)$ are considered to be only frequency-dependent, while the measured signals $X'(\tau, f)$, $Y'(\tau, f)$ and $Z'(\tau, f)$ acquire time dependence through the STFT segmentation. Consequently, each digitizer port receives a combination of the desired signal from its corresponding antenna and the contributions coupled from the other two antennas at each τ and f , expressed as:

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$$X'(\tau, f) = X(\tau, f) + k_{XY}(f) \cdot Y(\tau, f) + k_{XZ}(f) \cdot Z(\tau, f) \quad (15)$$

$$Y'(\tau, f) = Y(\tau, f) + k_{XY}(f) \cdot X(\tau, f) + k_{YZ}(f) \cdot Z(\tau, f) \quad (16)$$

$$Z'(\tau, f) = Z(\tau, f) + k_{YZ}(f) \cdot Y(\tau, f) + k_{XZ}(f) \cdot X(\tau, f) \quad (17)$$

where $X'(\tau, f)$, $Y'(\tau, f)$ and $Z'(\tau, f)$ are the signals measured on the three digitizer ports corresponding to $X(\tau, f)$, $Y(\tau, f)$ and $Z(\tau, f)$ magnetic field components, and $k_{XY}(f)$, $k_{XZ}(f)$ and $k_{YZ}(f)$ are the MC coefficients. The coefficients are obtained from the S21 parameter measurements shown in the previous section. Since the antennas interact with each other, the above set of equations forms a system of three unknowns at each time-frequency bin (τ, f) .

To find the original signals the matrix form is used. The matrix of coefficients is denoted as $M(f)$. The equation (15) - (17) can then be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X'(\tau, f) \\ Y'(\tau, f) \\ Z'(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} = M \cdot \begin{bmatrix} X(\tau, f) \\ Y(\tau, f) \\ Z(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where:

$$M(f) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{1} & k_{XY}(f) & k_{XZ}(f) \\ k_{XY}(f) & \mathbf{1} & k_{YZ}(f) \\ k_{XZ}(f) & k_{YZ}(f) & \mathbf{1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

To find the original signals X, Y and Z two matrixes should be multiplied:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X(\tau, f) \\ Y(\tau, f) \\ Z(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} = M(f)^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} X'(\tau, f) \\ Y'(\tau, f) \\ Z'(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Solving this matrix equation at each τ (time slice) and f (frequency bin) provides the original signals, removing the effect of mutual coupling through the entire measurement process.

B. Measurement setup

To validate the proposed compensation method, a MSLA and a multichannel digitizer are used. Low-noise preamplifiers were used between the antenna and the digitizer. Preamplifiers were validated to not introduce any phase shifts. Figure 110 shows the measurement setup. As a digitizer a PicoScope® 5444D MSO model was used [34]. The MSLA was connected to channels A, B, and C, respectively. A sampling frequency of 125 MS/s was chosen, that is four times higher than the highest measured frequency, to improve accuracy. The resolution of the digitizer was set to 8-bit. The software part for data gathering and post processing was written in Python. A magnetic field source was a shielded loop antenna facing the MSLA at a certain angle, specifically not aligned with any antenna in the MSLA construction, therefore generating all three X, Y, Z field components.

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From Figure 108 and Figure 109, the highest MC effect between antennas can be found at 30 MHz. Due to this, the 30 MHz frequency was chosen for the first measurement to validate the MC correction factor technique. The second set of measurements, aimed at showing deviations in the measurement results around the equipment under test (EUT), covered the entire frequency range from 150 kHz to 30 MHz, comparing a single SLA to the MSLA setup. To achieve this, a signal containing peaks at every 200 kHz was used.

Figure 110. Measurement setup: multi-axis antenna, preamplifier, digitizer, laptop

C. Validation for 30 MHz

The SLA used as the emission source and was positioned in a way that it emitted a high level of magnetic field in one axis, a smaller level in the second, and the lowest in the third [6]. This is one of the cases investigated in [27], which showed a high deviation in the measurement results of the antenna that picked up the lowest magnetic field level. Figure 110 demonstrates the effectiveness and importance of this MC correction technique. In Figure 111 each 3 bars represent measurement plane. The first bar in each 3 bars represent measurements with MSLA without implementation of the MC correction factor, the second reference measurement with a SLA, and the third one result of the MSLA measurement with implementation of the MC correction factor. In scenarios with high measurement signal of 55 dB μ A/m in the Z-axis (first 3 bars in the Figure 111) and 31 dB μ A/m in the X-axis (second 3 bars in the Figure 111), the outcomes remain remarkably consistent for SLA and MSLA with and without MC correction factor implementation. It is due to the fact that the magnetic field level on both of these antennas is comparable high and the MC connection will not have a significant impact on them. This consistency is due to the proposed antenna design that shows a low level of the MC coefficients (Figure 108 and Figure 109).

However, a weakest measurement results initially measured at 19.5 dB μ A/m in the Y-axis is influenced by the MSLA MC effect between XY and YZ antennas. With the implementation of the MC correction factor, the lowest level which was measured by the MSLA become consistent with the measurement results obtained by the SLA (last 2 bars Figure 111) and start to correspond to 14 dB μ A/m.

This scenario highlights the effectiveness of the proposed compensation method, as the MSLA construction amplifies the signal due to MC effects. However, if the phase shift between received signals on each axis differs, the MSLA may suppress the signal, leading to an underestimation of the MC level on one axis. By integrating the proposed MC correction factor with the standard antenna factor, high measurement precision is achieved, even for low-level signals, allowing the use of MSLA in other construction implementations, despite a possible stronger MC effects between antennas.

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Figure 111. Amplitude response for 30 MHz. Single antenna measurements in combination with MSLA with and without MC correction factor.

D. Measurement results around an EUT

To verify the effectiveness of this method across the entire frequency spectrum, the TX shielded loop antenna was angled and treated as an 'unidentified' magnetic field source. The EUT, in this case, a tilted SLA, was measured 12 times from different positions and orientation which is described in the standard method and 4 times with the proposed measurement method. The outcomes of these measurements are presented in Figure 112. Standards for magnetic field measurements typically concentrate on the highest level of emissions detected. Hence, the presentation of the measurement results highlighted the peak value from each axis across the four measurements positions.

The measurement results indicate a high degree of precision between the single shield loop antenna and the MSLA, with a minor deviation in peak measurement results of approximately 0.3-0.4 dB. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the measurement setup employing the MSLA is not only comparable to the standard measurement method but also offers advantages in terms of time savings and the capability to measure transient processes by the data recording which is provided by the digitizer.

2.3.3.4 Conclusion of Multi-channel MSLA time domain measurement method

Despite advantages, the MSLA system faces challenges related to the MC effect between antennas in the MSLA construction, which can introduce errors, particularly for the low-level measured signals. Without proper correction, these errors can lead to significant deviations in the measurement results. The MC correction factor which was shown in this study significantly reduces any influence of the MSLA construction on the measurement results. Enabling high measurement accuracy that competes with the standard SLA construction, further integration of the measurement methods is possible. In [35], the implementation of several multi-channel digitizers was demonstrated. By using synchronization and time stamps on the TD data, multiple multi-channel digitizers can be combined with several MSLA units placed around an EUT. This also allows higher sampling rates, and thus oversampling, which can increase the signal to noise ratio. Due to the relatively low cost of modern digitizers compared to multi-channel TD EMI receivers, the advantage of a such technique is high. Figure 113 shows the possible implementations of multiple MSLA units.

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Such a measurement setup, supported by the MC correction factor, can significantly decrease the evaluation time of the EUT. It enables tracking of the phase shift between each axis across the four measurement positions required by the standards simultaneously. Access to both the amplitude and phase behaviour around an EUT can provide valuable insights to development personnel on how to mitigate the outgoing magnetic field from the EUT, improving overall measurement efficiency and accuracy.

Figure 112. Measurement results around an EUT. The max hold of the four different positions around the EUT is presented for three antenna orientations, using both an SLA and an MSLA with the MC correction method.

Figure 113. Implementation of multiple digitizers in combination with several MSLA around the EUT.

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The MSLA construction combined with a multichannel digitizer represents a significant advancement in magnetic field measurements below 30 MHz. This innovative system evaluates all antenna orientations simultaneously, reducing measurement time drastically compared to traditional methods that use a single SLA (and a single-input conventional super-heterodyne receivers). By employing a MSLA and multi-channel TD measurements, the proposed measurement method provides comprehensive access to all three axes and additional phase shift information, resulting in enhanced measurement accuracy and mitigating the limitations of conventional single-axis measurement approaches.

Implementing an advanced MSLA MC correction factor which is shown in this research, achieves extreme accuracy in measurement results. While different antenna constructions can significantly vary the MC between antennas, the proposed correction method effectively mitigates these variations, allowing even non-ideal MSLA constructions to be used in measurement procedures.

The combination of the MSLA with multi-channel measurements using modern digitizers can reduce standard measurement times from hours to mere seconds. This innovation allows for more ideal measurement procedures, enabling evaluations based not only on single operational modes but also on real-world urban driving patterns without significantly increasing measurement time.

3. Results and Conclusion

The intended electromagnetic emissions measurement methods, optimised for the in situ assessment of large-scale/high-power equipment, have been successfully developed and applied in real-world use cases in collaboration with industry stakeholders. Relevant use cases include photovoltaic installations, large industrial machines using induction technology, and elements in singular scientific facilities, to name a few. The distilled test protocol has been drafted and is proposed for inclusion as the recommended procedure for the forthcoming CISPR 37 standard. The said procedure includes steps before, during and after the in situ measurement campaign. The method relies on time-domain measurements and software-based FFT receivers to accelerate the testing process, characterise variable ambient noise levels, and identify operating modes and conditions that maximise the likelihood of interference. The techniques employed readily enable transient event detection, with time-gating functionality to focus on or remove such events from the test results. All those methods are now automated in the emiGO software from EMC Barcelona. As a side contribution, distance conversion factors for adjusting the emissions limits from the reference distance to the actual measurement distance have been proposed. Results are presented in relevant sections separately.

The integration of MSLA (Multi-Sensor Loop Antenna) with a multichannel digitizer significantly improves magnetic field measurements below 30 MHz. Unlike traditional single-axis methods, this system measures all antenna orientations simultaneously, drastically reducing measurement time from hours to seconds. It provides full three-axis data and phase shift information, enhancing accuracy. An advanced MC correction factor further compensates for variations in antenna construction, enabling reliable results even with non-ideal setups. This innovation supports more realistic testing scenarios, such as urban driving patterns, without increasing measurement time.

In conclusion, this report presents findings on the traceable radiated electromagnetic emissions measurement methods optimised for in situ assessment of large-size/high power equipment, including validated test procedures along with the characterisation of influence factors and a measurement protocol for selecting adequate test setup (i.e., antenna location, height, and polarisation) and data from CISPR 37-based test site investigations, radiated emissions test results, including comparison data, and time domain technique for fast electrical and magnetic radiated emission testing to capture worst case emissions and short duration/transient interference.

Deliverable 2 of EMC-STD project has been successfully achieved and this document meets the objective 1 requirements committed in Annex 1 JRP Protocol.

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4. References

- [1] International Special Committee on Radio Interference “CISPR 16-1-1:2019 Ed 5.0. Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods - Part 1-1: Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - Measuring apparatus,” IEC, Geneva, CH, Standard, Jun. 2019.
- [2] International Special Committee on Radio Interference, “CISPR 37 ED1 Industrial, scientific and medical equipment - Radio-frequency disturbance characteristics - Limits and methods for measurements in situ,” International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva.
- [3] M. Pous, M. A. Azpúrua, and F. Silva, “Benefits of Full Time-domain EMI measurements for Large Fixed Installation,” in 2016 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility - EMC EUROPE, 2016. doi: 10.1109/EMCEurope.2016.7739221 pp. 514–519.
- [4] M. Pous, M. A. Azpúrua, J. A. Oliva, M. Aragón, I. González, and F. Silva, “Full Time-domain EMI measurement system applied to railway emissions according to IEC 62236-3-1 / EN 50121-3-1 standards,” in 2018 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC EUROPE), 2018. doi: 10.1109/EMCEurope.2018.8485173 pp. 260–265.
- [5] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, and F. Silva, “A Measurement System for Radiated Transient Electromagnetic Interference based on General Purpose Instruments,” in 2015 IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC), 2015. doi: 10.1109/ISEMC.2015.7256338 pp. 1189–1194.
- [6] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, J. A. Oliva, B. Pinter, M. Martin Hudlička, and F. Silva, “Waveform Approach for Assessing Conformity of CISPR 16-1-1 Measuring Receivers,” IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement, vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 1187–1198, 2018. doi: 10.1109/TIM.2018.2794941
- [7] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, and F. Silva, “A Single Antenna Ambient Noise Cancellation Method for In-situ Radiated EMI Measurements in the Time-domain,” in 2016 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility - EMC EUROPE, 2016. doi: 10.1109/EMCEurope.2016.7739185 pp. 501–506.
- [8] B. t. Have, T. Hartman, N. Moonen and F. Lefeber, “Static Energy Meters and the Electrical Environment Comply to the Standards But are Not Compatible,” in IEEE Electromagnetic Compatibility Magazine, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 59-68, 1st Quarter 2023, doi: 10.1109/MEMC.2023.10135174.
- [9] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, and F. Silva, “Specifying the Waveforms for the Calibration of CISPR 16-1-1 Measuring Receivers,” IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 654–662, 2020. doi: 10.1109/TEMC.2019.2923813.
- [10] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, M. Fernandez, and F. Silva, “Dynamic Performance Evaluation of Full Time-domain EMI Measurement Systems,” in 2018 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC EUROPE), 2018. doi: 10.1109/EMCEurope.2018.8485086 pp. 561–566.
- [11] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, and F. Silva, “Statistical Evaluation of Measurement Accuracy in Full Time-domain EMI Measurement Systems,” in 2020 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility - EMC EUROPE, 2020. pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/EMCEUROPE48519.2020.9245837.
- [12] International Special Committee on Radio Interference, “CISPR/1476/DC. Rapid Emissions Check for installations”, Document for Commenting, 03 2022.
- [13] International Special Committee on Radio Interference “CISPR 16-1-4 Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods - Part 1-4: Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus - Antennas and test sites for radiated disturbance measurements, International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, 2019

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co financed from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

- [14] International Special Committee on Radio Interference, “CISPR 11, Industrial, scientific and medical equipment-Radio-frequency disturbance characteristics-Limits and methods of measurement,” International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, 2017.
- [15] International Special Committee on Radio Interference, “Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods. Part 4-2, Uncertainties, statistics and limit modelling. Measurement instrumentation uncertainty.,” International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, 2011.
- [16] B. t. Have, M. A. Azpurua, T. Hartman, M. Pous, N. Moonen, F. Silva, and F. Leferink, “Waveform model to characterize time-domain pulses resulting in emi on static energy meters,” IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 1542–1549, 2021.
- [17] M. Lavielle, “Using penalized contrasts for the change-point problem,” Signal Processing, vol. 85, no. 8, pp. 1501–1510, 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165168405000381>
- [18] P. F. R. Killick and I. A. Eckley, “Optimal detection of changepoints with a linear computational cost,” Journal of the American Statistical Association, vol. 107, no. 500, pp. 1590–1598, 2012.
- [19] CISPR 16-2-3
- [20] J. Xu, F. Dai, D. Su, Q. Qiao, and H. Zheng, “Ambient noise cancellation in frequency domain EMI measurement,” in Proc. 4th IEEE Int. Symp. Microw. Antenna Propag. EMC Technol. Wireless Commun., 2011, pp. 555–558.
- [21] A. Frech, A. Zakaria, S. Braun, and P. Russer, “Ambient noise cancelation with a time-domain EMI measurement system using adaptive filtering,” in Proc. Asia-Pac. Symp. Electromagn. Compatibil. 19th Int. Zurich Symp. Electromagn. Compatibil., 2008, pp. 534–537.
- [22] A. Frech, S. Limmer, and P. Russer, “A novel real-time ambient noise cancellation system for emi measurements in time-domain,” in Proc. 10th Int. Symp. Electromagn. Compatibil., 2011, pp. 41–45.
- [23] A. Frech and P. Russer, “Real-time ambient noise cancellation for EMI measurements on open area test sites,” in Proc. Asia-Pac. Symp. Electromagn. Compatibil., 2012, pp. 213–216.
- [24] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, and F. Silva, “A measurement system for radiated transient electromagnetic interference based on general purpose instruments,” in Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Electromagn. Compatibil. (EMC), 2015, pp. 1189–1194.
- [25] M. A. Azpúrua, M. Pous, J. A. Oliva, B. Pinter, M. Hudlicka, and F. Silva, “Waveform approach for assessing conformity of CISPR 161-1 measuring receivers,” IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas., vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 1187–1198, May 2018.
- [26] C. Keyer, R. Timens, F. Buesink, and F. Leferink, “In-situ measurement of high frequency emission caused by photo voltaic inverters,” in Proc. Int. Symp. Electromagn. Compatibil., 2014, pp. 74–78.
- [27] D. Pokotilov, R. Vogt-Ardatjew, and F. Leferink, “Evaluation of three-axis magnetic loop antenna cross coupling for low-frequency measurements,” in Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Electromagn. Compat. Signal/Power Integrity, Aug. 2022, pp. 315–320, doi: 10.1109/EMCSI39492.2022.9889631.
- [28] D. Pokotilov, R. Vogt-Ardatjew, and F. Leferink, “Estimation of the highest influence on the measured results of a three-axis shielded loop antenna using three transmitting antenna and tilted antenna methods,” in Proc. Int. Symp. Electromagn. Compat. – EMC Europe, IEEE, 2022, pp. 237–241, doi: 10.1109/EMCEurope51680.2022.9901249.

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co financed from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

- [29] J. Volakis, Antenna Engineering Handbook. 4th ed. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, Jun. 2007, pp. 94–103.
- [30] G. P. Arada and T. Hirano, “The effects of varying the location of antenna feed gaps on MC between orthogonal circular loops,” in Proc. Int. Conf. Electron., Inf., Commun., Jan. 2020, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICEIC49074.2020.9051023.
- [31] O. Sen and S. Cakir, “Loop antenna calibrations with inclusion of vector network analyser and comparison between calibration methods,” in Proc. Int. Symp. Electromagn. Compat., Nov. 2017, pp. 1–5, 10.1109/EMCEurope.2017.8094694.
- [32] M. Ishii and K. Komiyama, “A measurement method for magnetic antenna factor of small circular loop antenna by 3-antenna method,” in Proc. URSI. North Amer. Radio Sci. Meeting (Columbus), Jul. 2003, Art. no. 458.
- [33] M. Ishii and K. Komiyama, “Estimation of uncertainty of calibration for loop antennas by three-antenna method using automatic network analyzer,” in Proc. 67th ARFTG Conf., Jun. 2006, pp. 156–163.
- [34] PicoScope 5000 series datasheet, Sept 2019, [online] Available: <https://www.picotech.com/download/datasheets/picoscope-5000d-series-data-sheet.pdf>.
- [35] A. Matthee, N. Moonen, and F. Leferink, “Synchronous Multipoint Low-Frequency EMI Measurement and Applications,” IEEE Letters on Electromagnetic Compatibility Practice and Applications, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 120-124, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1109/LEMCPA.2022.3218320.

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